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Report on trends in policies and practices on the use of LLMs and generative AI in partnership -Second report-

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Executive Summary

This report examines current developments and temporal changes in the use of Large Language Models (LLMs) and Generative Artificial Intelligence (GenAI) in higher education across institutions participating in the ADMIT project (Generative AI and Large Language Models in Higher Education). The analysis draws on both quantitative and qualitative data collected from key stakeholder groups, including students, educators, IT and support staff, and administrative personnel. The findings highlight considerable differences in awareness, usage, and institutional approaches to integrating AI technologies into educational contexts.

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1. Introduction

The integration of Large Language Models (LLMs) and Generative Artificial Intelligence (GenAI) is increasingly influencing higher education by reshaping learning activities, course design, and institutional leadership. As universities respond to this changing technological landscape, they are developing a range of policies and practices that reflect both the opportunities and challenges associated with these tools. This report presents current developments and trends in the use of LLM models and GenAI in the context of education. The information presented here was collected in 2025 from higher education institutions participating in the ADMIT project (Generative AI and Large Language Models in Higher Education, 2024-2026). The development of these perspectives will be monitored over a three-year period.

This report presents the second annual overview of policies and practices related to the use of LLMs and GenAI in educational settings, including learning activities, course design, and leadership contexts. It examines emerging opportunities and challenges, while also tracing the development of these technologies over time. To support this analysis, data was collected through online questionnaires targeting a range of stakeholders, including students, teachers, IT personnel, and institutional leaders in administration. Within this framework, the report provides a snapshot of how LLMs and GenAI are currently addressed in policies and practices across the participating institutions and countries. The questionnaires used were similar to the first year's data collection (Koçdar et al., 2025) in most parts.

1.1. Aim of the report

The purpose of this report is twofold. First, it aims to map the institutional policies and practices related to GenAI and LLMs, such as ChatGPT, in the universities participating in the project. Second, it seeks to investigate how these technologies are perceived and experienced by different stakeholder groups, namely students, teachers, IT support personnel, and administrative staff. Particular attention is paid to their levels of awareness, perceived challenges, and perceived opportunities in relation to institutional responses. Based on this framework, the report addresses the following five research questions.

Research Question 1: To what extent are the four groups of academic users aware of individual, institutional and national policies and practices regarding the use of GenAI in higher education?

Research Question 2: For what specific educational purposes do the four groups of academic users currently use or plan to use LLMs and GenAI?

Research Question 3: What opportunities do the four groups of academic users identify in relation to individual, institutional and national policies and practices concerning the use of GenAI in higher education?

Research Question 4: What challenges do the four groups of academic users describe concerning individual, institutional and national policies and practices governing the use of GenAI in higher education?

Research Question 5: How has the awareness and use of artificial intelligence in higher education changed across the ADMIT partner institutions between 2024 and 2025?

2. Methodology

2.1. Research design

The purpose of this report was to examine awareness, policies and practices concerning the use of LLMs and GenAI across the universities participating in the ADMIT project. To support this objective, both quantitative and qualitative data were gathered to provide insights into the subject matter. Data was collected between May and September of 2025.

2.2. Participants

The data were collected from the following 10 partner universities: Anadolu University (AU)- TR, Fern Universität in Hagen (FERNUNI)- DE, Hellenic Open University (HOU)- GR, University of Jyväskylä (JYU)- FI, Open University of Cyprus (OUC)- CY, Open University of the United Kingdom (OUUK)- UK, Universidad Nacional de Educación a Distancia (UNED)- SP, UniDistance Suisse (UNIDISTANCE)- CH, Università Telematica Internazionale (UNINETTUNO)- IT, and Fundació per a la Universitat Oberta de Catalunya (UOC)- SP. The purposive sampling method was employed to select participants who use AI tools, aiming to gather more data on individual, institutional, and national policies and practices.

The population was composed of 523 participants belonging to different categories and specifically: 24 administrative staff, 27 IT/support staff, 126 teachers, and 346 students, who completed the questionnaires. Table 1 presents the distribution of data regarding partner universities.

Table 1- The Distribution of Data within Partner Universities

Institution	Administration	IT/Support Staff	Teachers	Students
AU	2	2	10	21
FERNUNI	2	4	10	50
HOU	2	2	10	44
JYU	2	2	9	20
OUC	3	2	11	42
OUUK	2	3	20	26
UNED	3	2	20	50
UNIDISTANCE	1	2	9	61
UNINETTUNO	4	6	17	18
UOC	3	2	10	3
Total	24	27	126	346

2.3. Data collection tools

In collaboration EADTU, AU, JYU and OUC representatives designed and developed online questionnaires to gather information on policies and practices within the partnership. Four questionnaires (see Appendices A, B, C, and D) were used to collect data on individual, institutional and national awareness and usage of practices and/or policies regarding the use of LLMs or GenAI among the following stakeholder groups:

- **Administration/University Management:** This group included rectors, vice-rectors, directors, deans, and other individuals qualified to respond to questions about national, institutional, and individual policies and practices within the institution. If multiple respondents were needed for the questionnaire, it was recommended that relevant individuals complete it.
- **IT/Teaching and Learning Support Services:** This group included managers, deputy managers, directors, deputy directors, and staff from support departments, IT support departments, and departments dedicated to LLM and GenAI. Additional respondents from different departments could be included as needed.
- **Teachers:** It was recommended to involve teachers from various faculties, if possible.
- **Students:** It was recommended to involve students from different levels of study and faculties, if possible.

The questionnaires consisted of three sections—individual, institutional, and national levels—focused on awareness, purpose of use, opportunities, and challenges, featuring 14 closed- and open-ended questions in alignment with the research questions. Three questions consisted of comparisons with the previous year as regards personal/institution/national usage of LLMs or GenAI tools for teaching, learning, or research. Consent forms were prepared for the questionnaires (see Appendix E).

2.4. Data collection process

A Data Collection Guide was updated from last year's version (Koçdar et al., 2025), including guidelines for online questionnaires. Each partner was expected to collect data within their respective institutions from May to June 2025 across all relevant stakeholders. Ethical approval documents for data collection were provided to each institution individually.

Data collection involved online questionnaires, administered to each stakeholder group. The questionnaires, developed in online Google Forms, were provided to partners and administered anonymously. A consent form for questionnaires was required. Questionnaire questions were presented only to those who accepted the consent form.

In last year’s data collection process, variations in sample sizes across stakeholders and universities posed a limitation to the generalizability of the quantitative findings, as noted in the report (Koçdar et al., 2025). To address this issue, the maximum number of stakeholders has been set in order to ensure more comparable sample sizes for the second report. However, if a stakeholder provided a sample size that deviated just slightly from the expected maximum or minimum, the data was included in the analysis as a whole and the effect of stakeholder (institution) was controlled in the analysis (please, see 2.5.2.). Table 2 below summarizes the data collection tools as well as the minimum and maximum expected number of stakeholders at each partner university.

Table 2- Minimum and maximum number of participants required for the questionnaire at each partner university.

Stakeholders		Minimum expected number of participants	Maximum expected number of participants
Administration/ University Management	University management: rectors, vice-rectors, deans, etc., the person who is eligible to answer questions about institutional and individual policies and practices in the institution. If more than one person needs to respond to the questionnaire, please have the relevant individuals fill it out.	2	3
IT/Teaching and learning support services	Managers, vice managers, directors, vice directors, etc. of support departments, IT support departments, departments dedicated to LLM and GenAI, etc. If needed, more people can be involved from different departments.	2	3
Teachers	Teachers from different faculties, if possible.	10	20
Students	Students from different levels of study and faculties, if possible.	20	50

Additionally, a short questionnaire was prepared and sent to partner institutions to gather further information on whether there had been any changes since last year in current policies and practices regarding the use of LLMs and GenAI tools (Appendix F). The purpose of this questionnaire was to complement and validate the responses collected from students, teachers, administrators, and support staff. Each ADMIT partner institution was asked to conduct a brief review of their institutional and national data to ensure an accurate and up-to-date reflection of policies and practices. It should be emphasized that the findings are presented in chapter 3.6. (Additional results regarding institutional and national policies and practices) are derived exclusively from the input of one representative per ADMIT partner institution.

2.5. Data analysis

2.5.1. Quantitative analysis for group comparisons, and descriptive statistics

To investigate whether questionnaire answers differed across participant groups (student, teacher, IT/support, administration) in 2025, a Kruskal-Wallis test was conducted and all pairwise comparisons were carried out with Bonferroni correction.

In question “*Compared to your situation a year ago, have you noticed any changes in the way you use LLMs or Generative AI tools for studying or research?*” a response option “*I do not use them at all*” was excluded from the analysis because it does not reflect a change in usage over time, but rather a categorical absence of use. Including this option would have introduced conceptual ambiguity, as it cannot be meaningfully placed on the same ordinal scale as the other options, which specifically describe relative changes in usage compared to one year ago. To ensure the validity of the statistical comparisons and maintain the interpretability of the results, only responses indicating a change (or no change) in usage were included in the analysis. On the same basis, in question “*Compared to a year ago, have you noticed any changes in the way your institution uses LLMs or GenAI tools for studying or research?*” option “*I have no idea*” was excluded from the Wilcoxon signed-rank test.

2.5.2. Quantitative analysis for group and temporal comparisons between data collection sets of 2024 and 2025, and descriptive statistics

In our previous report (Koçdar et al., 2025), a similar questionnaire than now was used during spring and summer of 2024 to address most of the research questions. The only difference in participant institutes is that this year Open Universiteit Nederland (OUNL) is not included in the data. For the purposes of analyzing the temporal change of awareness and use of AI in higher education in our partner institutions from 2024 to 2025, the year of the data set (2024, 2025) and group (student, teacher, IT/support, administration) were used as categorical predictors in General Linear Model (GLM), with questionnaire items treated as dependent variables (for more information about the data set, please, see Koçdar et al., 2025). The analysis was performed in IBM SPSS Statistics, utilizing the likelihood ratio estimation method for model parameters.

To address potential bias stemming from unequal sample sizes across partner institutions, a stratified bootstrapping procedure with 1,000 resamples was applied. This approach was used to evaluate the robustness of parameter estimates and to generate 95% confidence intervals for each group. Bootstrapping, with institution as a strata variable, was also applied when reporting descriptives without dividing users into groups. Although the dependent variables were measured using a 4- or 5- or 6-point Likert scale (ordinal), mean values and parametric analyses were used based on the assumption of approximate interval-level properties, supported by the sample size and distribution characteristics.

2.5.3. Qualitative Data Analysis

A content analysis was conducted to examine the qualitative data derived from the open-ended questionnaire responses. In accordance with the principles of qualitative research, the analysis emphasized the contextual richness and subjective meanings of the responses. The approach was interpretive and inductive, with themes emerging from the data rather than using predefined categories. Quotations from stakeholders across different universities were included to illustrate the diversity of perspectives, with pseudonyms assigned to ensure anonymity. Where appropriate, AI tools such as Microsoft Copilot Pro and Gemini were employed to support the analysis process. To enhance the reliability of the findings, all analyses were subsequently peer-reviewed by another researcher.

3. Results

3.1. The results regarding familiarity with LLMs and GenAI

3.1.1. Students were least familiar with AI in 2025

To examine group-level differences in familiarity with LLMs and GenAI in 2025, a non-parametric Kruskal-Wallis test was conducted. The test revealed a statistically significant difference between groups ($H(3) = 26.922, p < .001$). Post hoc tests revealed that Students reported significantly lower familiarity with AI than Teachers (adjusted $p = .000$), IT/Support (adjusted $p = .002$), and Administration (unadjusted $p = .032$, adjusted $p = .191$).

Figure 1- Familiarity with LLMs and GenAI

3.1.2. The overall familiarity with LLMs and GenAI increased from 2024 to 2025

A General Linear Model (GLM) was used to examine participants' familiarity with LLMs and GenAI. The dependent variable was measured using a 4-point Likert scale (1 = not familiar, 4 = very familiar). Although ordinal, mean values and parametric methods were applied under the assumption of approximate interval-level properties.

The analysis revealed a statistically significant effect of Year ($F(1, 2041) = 9.705, p = .002, \eta^2 = .005$), indicating that familiarity increased from 2024 ($M = 2.84$) to 2025 ($M = 3.17$). Group differences were also significant ($F(3, 2041) = 26.759, p < .001, \eta^2 = .038$). Post hoc comparisons using Bonferroni correction showed that Students reported significantly lower familiarity than all other groups: compared to Teachers (mean difference = $-0.49, p < .001$), IT/Support (mean difference = $-0.85, p < .001$), and Administration (mean difference = $-0.62, p < .001$). Additionally, Teachers reported significantly lower familiarity than IT/Support (mean difference = $-0.37, p = .045$). No statistically significant differences were found between the Administration group with either the Teacher or IT/support groups.

The interaction between Year and Group was not statistically significant ($F(3, 2041) = 0.496, p = .685$), suggesting that the increase in familiarity over time was consistent across all groups.

Table 3- Participants' familiarity with LLMs and GenAI from 2024 to 2025

Group	2024 Mean	2024 SE	2025 Mean	2025 SE
Student	2.399	0.025	2.818	0.049
Teacher	2.855	0.060	3.190	0.080
IT/Support	3.261	0.188	3.407	0.174
Administration	2.846	0.250	3.250	0.184

3.1.3. Students received less training or support related to LLMs and GenAI than some other professional groups in 2025

To assess whether different participant groups received varying levels of training or support related to the use of LLMs and GenAI tools, a Kruskal-Wallis test was conducted. The results indicated a statistically significant difference between groups ($H(3) = 15.084, p = .002$), suggesting that the distribution of responses was not the same across all groups.

Pairwise comparisons with Bonferroni correction revealed that Students reported significantly less training or support compared to Teachers (adjusted $p = .020$) and IT/Support staff (adjusted $p = .047$). The difference between Students and Administration was not statistically significant after correction (adjusted $p = .611$). No significant differences were found between Teachers, Administration, and IT/Support staff.

These findings indicate that Students had received less training or support related to LLMs and GenAI than some other professional groups, particularly Teachers and IT/Support staff.

Figure 2 – Received training or support related to the use of LLMs or GenAI

3.1.4. The overall level of training or support did not change significantly from 2024 to 2025

A General Linear Model (GLM) was conducted to examine whether participants’ reported training or support related to LLMs and GenAI differed by year (2024 vs. 2025) and participant group (Student, Teacher, IT/Support, Admin). The analysis revealed a statistically significant main effect of group ($F(3, 2039) = 16.979, p < .001, \eta^2 = .024$), indicating that the level of training or support varied between groups. However, there was no significant effect of year ($F(1, 2039) = 0.366, p = .545$), and no significant interaction between year and group ($F(3, 2039) = 0.169, p = .917$). These results suggest that the differences between groups were consistent across both years.

3.1.5. Received training or support (open-ended answers)

The open-ended answers for the question “Have you received any training (formal or informal course, etc.) or support (teacher/expert/peer guidance, learning resources, etc.) related to the use of LLMs or generative AI tools?” were divided into two categories: Formal and informal training/support. Formal training/support is classified as structured learning experiences that are generally provided by educational institutions, professional organizations, or training providers. These training sessions are typically planned, scheduled, and delivered by qualified instructors or experts in the field. On the other hand, informal training can be defined as unstructured learning experiences outside formal educational settings and often driven by the individual's own interests and needs.

As previously mentioned, responses from all the stakeholders including students, teachers, IT/Support Staff, and administrators are categorized as formal and informal training/support. A summary is given below.

Students

Formal Training/Support: Face-to-face and online workshops, seminars, e-learning conferences, university-organized courses on AI, courses on platforms like Coursera.

Informal Training/Support: Hands-on experience with AI tools like ChatGPT and Poe.com, learning by collaborating with peers, exploring AI through blogs and online resources, and watching explanatory YouTube videos.

Teachers

Formal Training/Support: Seminars provided by universities, webinars, and workshops about some GenAI tools.

Informal Training/Support: Guidance from colleagues, self-learning via YouTube videos, participation in informal Zoom meetings, participation in informal academic discussions, and independently exploring AI tools for instructional material development.

IT/Support

Formal Training/Support: Technical workshops and courses, institutional webinars on AI, participation in conferences focused on digital technologies in education, and AI-related training courses at the university.

Informal Training/Support: Exploration of online resources like tutorials and blogs, peer-guided learning within IT teams, and hands-on self-learning of GenAI tools through direct use.

Administrators

Formal Training/Support: Participation in internal institutional training sessions such as “JYU internal training on the possibilities of GenAI,” and external events discussing AI integration in educational contexts.

Informal Training/Support: *Not clearly represented in the responses.*

3.2. The results regarding awareness of individual, institutional, and national policies and practices

Research Question 1: To what extent are the four groups of academic users aware of individual, institutional and national policies and practices regarding the use of GenAI in higher education?

3.2.1. The users of AI didn't differ in their compliance of rules in 2025

A Kruskal-Wallis H test was conducted to examine differences between groups in their reported adherence to standards, rules, or policies when using LLMs or GenAI tools in studying or research. The test revealed a statistically significant difference between groups, $\chi^2(3) = 8.80, p = .032$, indicating that the distribution of responses varied across the groups. However, pairwise comparisons showed that none of the group differences reached statistical significance at the adjusted threshold.

Figure 3 - Compliance of rules

3.2.2. The compliance of standards, rules, or policies increased from 2024 to 2025

A general linear model (GLM) was conducted to examine the effects of year, group, and their interaction on responses to the question: “Do you follow specific standards, rules, or policies while using LLMs or Generative AI tools in studying or research?”.

The overall model was statistically significant, $F(7, 1953) = 14.62$, $p < .001$, with an R^2 of .050 (adjusted $R^2 = .046$), indicating that approximately 5% of the variance in responses was explained by the predictors. There was a significant main effect of year, $F(1, 1953) = 18.16$, $p < .001$, partial $\eta^2 = .009$. Participants in 2025 ($M = 2.67$, $SE = 0.086$) reported following standards more often than those in 2024 ($M = 2.10$, $SE = 0.102$), and this difference was confirmed by bootstrap confidence intervals. The main effect of group was not statistically significant, $F(3, 1953) = 0.87$, $p = .457$, partial $\eta^2 = .001$, nor was the interaction between year and group, $F(3, 1953) = 1.53$, $p = .204$, partial $\eta^2 = .002$.

3.2.3. Compliance of rules (open-ended answers)

The participants who answered “Yes, I strictly adhere to available standards, rules, or policies” or “Yes, I adhere to them to some extent” to the question “Do you follow specific standards, rules, or policies while using LLMs or Generative AI tools in teaching, learning, or research?” specified details about these standards, rules, or policies in the next step. A content analysis of the answers related to compliance with standards, rules, and policies related to LLMs or GenAI tool use is summarized, and examples are used to point out the category. (Pseudonyms are used in order to preserve the anonymity of the participants.)

Compliance with Standards: Respondents stated policies, regulations, rules, and principles established by their institutions or countries. It was a common theme among participants.

Diana (Teacher): *I strictly adhere to our university's existing general guidelines on the use of artificial intelligence. My own department also has specific guidelines on the use of artificial intelligence in language and communication studies, which I follow in my own teaching and which I also use to instruct my own students.*

John (Teacher): *There are comprehensive guidelines and a guideline for action from the FernUni.*

Brian (Administrator): *I follow the principles in Academic Integrity and Transparency in AI-assisted Research and Specification (aiTARAS) Framework.*

Jen (IT/Support): *I follow the OU staff policy... I don't like the idea of using it indiscriminately.*

Fact-Checking and Critical Thinking: The other theme that is stated by many participants is verifying the accuracy of AI-generated content and not copying AI-generated text directly.

Seth (Student): *I do not copy and paste anything from GenAI tools. I consider their output, check if it is correct and then maybe use the idea they provide me with. I purposefully avoid getting anything word-for-word from LLMs in my academic work.*

Donna (Teacher): *I never use literal aspects of AI & always check the possible accuracy of the statement.*

Maurice (IT/Support): *Be critical with results, don't feed in personal or classified data/information, check resources given, use versions and options to not let the LLMs use my usage data and conversations for further training, don't overuse (environmental and ethical concerns)*

Ethical Use: Many respondents frequently mentioned ethical use, including the avoidance of plagiarism. They stated the importance of citing properly and clearly indicating the use of AI.

Tom (Student): *I am not fully knowledgeable of all the rules, but I strive not to use the technology for unethical purposes (such as plagiarism, generating offensive content, etc.).*

Hans (Teacher): *A strict usage framework to ensure that tools are used as complementary and ancillary implementation and productivity tools, but without over-reliance and blind trust in them which can create ethical and moral issues (e.g. plagiarism), adoption and transfer of incorrect information.*

Kim (IT/Support): *I pay close attention to rules and principles, with a primary focus on the sensitivity of personal data and adherence to ethical guidelines. These are the key standards that guide my practices.*

Jan (Administrator): *There are no specific rules; however, I try to use them within the generally accepted framework of ethical principles in research.*

Data Protection and Privacy: Avoiding revealing personal data and violating copyrights while using AI are highly mentioned, especially among students.

Kim (Student): *I do not disclose personal data, I verify the accuracy of the responses, and I do not grant access to personal files.*

Shaun (Student): *I do not feed any personal data. Under no circumstances do I feed my employer's sensitive data.*

Michael (Teacher): *I do not process any personal data and do not share any texts with the tools for which I do not have a corresponding right of use.*

Angela (IT/Support): *This particularly concerns the use of data relevant to data protection; e.g. personal data is removed or pseudonymized.*

Gary (Administrator): *Material containing personal data may not be processed.*

3.2.4. Self-reported change in personal use of AI was in slight increase from 2024 to 2025

A Kruskal-Wallis test was conducted to determine differences between groups in responses to the question: "Compared to your situation a year ago, have you noticed any changes in the way you use LLMs or Generative AI tools for studying or research?" The test statistic was $\chi^2(3) = 0.33$, $p = .954$, with the statistic adjusted for ties. The result was not statistically significant, indicating that the distribution of responses did not differ significantly across the groups.

However, the overall use of AI has increased. A one-sample Wilcoxon signed-rank test was conducted to examine whether the median response differed from the hypothetical median of 3: “No, my use has remained the same”. Answers “I do not use them at all” were excluded (for more information, see 2.5. Data analysis). Among students, the observed median was 4 (“Yes, I use them slightly more than a year ago”), and the responses were significantly higher than the hypothetical median, $W = 22881$, $SE = 902.48$, $z = 12.13$, $p < .001$. Teachers ($N = 107$) also reported an observed median of 4, which was significantly greater than the hypothetical median, $W = 3256.5$, $SE = 205.75$, $z = 7.76$, $p < .001$. Similarly, IT staff ($N = 25$) had an observed median of 4, with a significant result, $W = 197$, $SE = 25.91$, $z = 3.55$, $p < .001$. Administrative staff ($N = 24$) also showed an observed median of 4, and the test indicated a significant difference from the hypothetical median, $W = 203.5$, $SE = 25.91$, $z = 3.80$, $p < .001$.

Figure 4 – The Change in the way respondents used LLMs or GenAI tools for studying or research compared to the last year

3.2.5. The change in the way respondents used LLMs or Generative AI tools for studying or research compared to the last year (open-ended answers)

Participants who responded to the question “Compared to your situation a year ago, have you noticed any changes in the way you use LLMs or Generative AI tools for teaching, learning, or research?”. and those who answered “Yes”, specified their answers in the next step. A summary of the answers is given below.

More frequent use in daily tasks: When asked to compare their way of use of AI tools with last year, participants indicated that they used AI tools more frequently in daily tasks this year. Due to their ability to speed up the process, AI tools have become widespread and are a part of everyday work.

John (Student): *I rely on it on a daily basis and am actively encouraged to use it at work which increases my appetite to use it more regularly outside of work due to speed of receiving answers as opposed to searching page after page after page on a search engine.*

Sara (IT/Support): *I now use ChatGPT on a daily basis as above examples show. I find it speeds up processes considerably.*

Harry (Administrator): *I use LLMs or Generative AI tools in my daily work, mainly to generate new ideas for initiating tasks or projects and to create the associated documentation.*

Change in attitude: Participants' statements regarding changes in attitudes towards AI tools and their intended use are given below. It is obvious that the way they see and use AI tools has changed.

Colin (Teacher): *At first, I was a bit skeptical and didn't use them at all, but now I'm more aware of their value and I use them.*

Donald (Student): *In the beginning, it was more of an aimless gimmick and "finding out what the AI can do"; now I use it in a targeted and professional way, also in a professional context.*

Pam (IT/Support): *In the past year, I've realized how the AI tool or LLMs can be very useful to speed up a task or to get a different perspective from my own. I never use AI tool as copy-paste but always as a starting point of something.*

More intensive use for research: Based on the answers provided, AI tools are progressively used in research processes, for example, in tasks such as generating drafts, summarizing articles, and conducting literature reviews.

Anthony (Teacher): *Over the past year, my use of AI tools as a researcher has evolved in both scope and sophistication. Initially, I relied on these tools primarily for basic tasks like summarizing academic articles, rephrasing text, or generating initial drafts of abstracts. However, with continued advancements in LLMs, their role in my research workflow has expanded to include more complex and high-value tasks. For example, I generate summaries of academic articles, draft and refine interview questions, survey instruments, and feedback forms.*

Mary (Student): *For example, I search and select the relevant literature for my work faster, I don't have to read the whole article, I have the summary with AI and I can understand whether this article is useful or not.*

Aidan (IT/Support): *I find myself using AI more and more because it's now integrated into common office software, much like how word processors or spreadsheets are standard tools. For instance, I'm currently experimenting with Gemini, which is integrated into Google Workspace. This means AI capabilities are directly available within the applications I already use for daily tasks.*

Integration into education: Direct integration of these tools into learning and teaching in areas such as producing course materials, developing interactive activities, and preparing exams is seen. Teachers and students emphasized using AI tools significantly more than a year ago.

Ken (Teacher): *I am more open to the tools, I know more tools, I use the tools more specifically and comprehensively in teaching (e.g., critical evaluation of texts created with GenAI, automated feedback)*

Mary (Student): *For example, I use LLMs to have complicated passages in the text prepared for me and use ChatGPT as a complete replacement for the course units in maths, because the course units are completely over-the-top incomprehensible. I upload the KEs and then go through the course units with ChatGPT based on them and have the topics explained to me in a way that suits my level of knowledge. The AI can explain maths perfectly, the professor refused to change his approach in any way in the past.*

3.2.6. Most of the students were unaware of institutional practices in 2025

An independent-samples Kruskal–Wallis test was conducted to examine whether perceptions of institutional practices related to the use of GenAI tools differed across groups. The results indicated a statistically significant difference between groups, $H(3) = 74.72, p < .001$ (adjusted for ties). Pairwise comparisons revealed that students rated institutional practices significantly lower than teachers ($z = -6.38, p < .001$), administrative staff ($z = -4.89, p < .001$), and IT/support staff ($z = -5.21, p < .001$). No statistically significant differences were found between the other groups.

Are there any institutional practices (e.g. virtual assistant, automated grading, personalized learning, etc.) regarding the use of LLMs or Generative AI tools in your institution

Figure 5 – Awareness of institutional practices

3.2.7. Students rated the awareness level of institutional practices significantly lower than all other groups in both years

A univariate general linear model (GLM) was conducted to examine the effects of group and year on perceptions of institutional practices related to the use of GenAI tools. The model was statistically significant, $F(7, 1994) = 71.63, p < .001$, with an explained variance of 20.1% ($R^2 = .201$, adjusted $R^2 = .198$). There was a significant main effect of group, $F(3, 1994) = 112.64, p < .001$, partial $\eta^2 = .145$, indicating substantial differences between groups. The effect of year was also significant, $F(1, 1994) = 4.32, p = .038$, partial $\eta^2 = .002$, suggesting a small but statistically detectable change over time. The interaction between year and group approached significance, $F(3, 1994) = 2.57, p = .053$, partial $\eta^2 = .004$.

The post hoc comparisons revealed that group membership had a clear and consistent effect on perceptions of institutional practices related to GenAI. Students rated institutional practices significantly lower than all other groups in both years, with the largest differences observed between students and IT/support staff (mean difference = $-1.63, p < .001$) and students and administrative staff (mean difference = $-1.39, p < .001$). Teachers also rated practices lower than IT/support staff (mean difference = $0.54, p = .003$), but the difference between teachers and administrative staff was not statistically significant.

The effect of the Year was statistically significant but modest in size. Across all groups, ratings were slightly higher in 2025 compared to 2024, suggesting a small overall increase in perceived institutional engagement with GenAI tools. However, the interaction between year and group was only marginally significant ($p = .053$), indicating that the change over time was relatively consistent across groups and did not substantially alter the group differences.

Table 4- Awareness level of institutional practices in 2025 compared to 2024

Group	2024 Mean	2024 SE	2025 Mean	2025 SE
Student	1,37	0,03	1,74	0,06
Teacher	2,52	0,08	2,57	0,12
IT/Support	3,09	0,23	3,07	0,22
Administration	2,46	0,35	3,04	0,23

3.2.8. Awareness of institutional practices (open-ended answers)

Examples of answers of those who answered "Yes, ..." to the question "Are there any institutional practices (e.g. virtual assistant, automated grading, personalized learning, etc.) regarding the use of LLMs or Generative AI tools in your institution?" are given below. Participants stated that some applications, virtual assistants or AI-powered chatbots were used to provide student support in their university.

Jess (Administrator): *There is a virtual assistant which is used for administrative student support for distance learners; however, it is rule-based; not generative. There are projects that test the use of generative AI in learning environments. An Artificial Intelligence Center has recently been founded.*

Mike (IT/Support): For example: COFFEE application, which provides students with automated feedback on the texts they have written. COFFEE is used in the English courses offered by English Learning Support, among other places.

Dan (IT/Support): There are pilot projects happening to trial institutional tools such as AIDA (Artificial Intelligence Digital Assistant) to support students as a study buddy, and AIMWA (Artificial Intelligence Module Writing Assistant) to support staff in creating and reworking content.

3.2.9. Students have generally poor knowledge about institutional policies and policies are overall not perceived as clearly defined

The Kruskal–Wallis test indicated a statistically significant difference between groups in their perceptions of institutional policies related to the use of GenAI tools, $H(3) = 26.70$, $p < .001$. Post hoc comparisons showed that students reported significantly lower awareness of such policies compared to teachers ($p = .002$) and administrative staff ($p = .001$). The difference between students and IT/support staff was not statistically significant after Bonferroni correction ($p = .115$). No significant differences were found between teachers, IT/support, and administrative staff.

In your knowledge, are there any institutional policies (rules, standards, recommendations, guidelines, regulations, etc.) in your institution related to the use of LLMs or Generative AI tools?

Figure 6 – Awareness of institutional policies

3.2.10. In 2025, respondents reported slightly higher awareness of institutional policies related to GenAI compared to 2024

The general linear model revealed a statistically significant effect of both group and year on perceptions of institutional policies related to GenAI, with the model explaining 22.7% of the variance ($R^2 = .227$). The effect of group was substantial ($F(3, 1987) = 71.73, p < .001, \text{partial } \eta^2 = .098$), indicating clear differences between respondent groups. The effect of year was statistically significant but small ($F(1, 1987) = 12.46, p < .001, \text{partial } \eta^2 = .006$), suggesting a slight increase in perceived policy presence in 2025 compared to 2024. Additionally, the interaction between year and group was significant ($F(3, 1987) = 6.19, p < .001, \text{partial } \eta^2 = .009$), indicating that the change over time varied somewhat across groups.

Post hoc comparisons showed that students consistently reported significantly lower awareness of institutional policies than all other groups ($p < .001$ for all comparisons). Teachers also reported lower awareness than administrative staff ($p < .001$) and IT/support staff ($p = .008$). No significant difference was found between IT/support and administrative staff ($p = 1.000$).

Table 5- Reported awareness of institutional policies across both years

Group	2024 Mean	2024 SE	2025 Mean	2025 SE
Student	1.38	0.03	2.46	0.09
Teacher	2.55	0.10	3.13	0.13
IT/Support	3.43	0.31	3.33	0.27
Administration	3.31	0.42	3.83	0.24

3.2.11. Awareness of institutional policies (open-ended answers)

The participants who said "Yes, ..." to the question "In your knowledge, are there any institutional policies (rules, standards, recommendations, guidelines, regulations, etc.) in your institution related to the use of LLMs or Generative AI tools?" were asked to specify their answers. Examples of answers are shown below.

Samantha (IT/Support): There are handouts and guidelines that I helped develop, but they often do not provide clear answers...

Walter (Administrator): AI guidelines of the FernUni, some of which are being developed or expanded.

Kurt (Administrator): There is a guideline for ethical use in thesis/dissertations.

A summary of the responses from the participants includes guidelines, prohibitions, and recommendations. Various universities have published guidelines and policies for the ethical use of AI, such as Anadolu University, Fern Universität in Hagen, University of Jyväskylä, and Open University of Cyprus. For instance, the use of Copilot has been recommended and supported by the University of Jyväskylä. On the other hand, there are some policies and rules on lower levels about what is allowed and what is restricted while using AI. Students are required to state a disclaimer if AI has been used in their work. But more strategies and policies are currently being developed.

3.2.12. Across all respondent groups, there was a perception that institutional use of AI tools has increased over the past year.

In one-sample Wilcoxon signed-rank test answers “I have no idea” were excluded (for more information, see 2.5. Data analysis). Among teachers, IT/support staff, and administrative staff, the observed median was 4, and the results showed statistically significant differences from the hypothetical median of 3: teachers (N = 92), W = 1,522.5, SE = 115.04, z = 6.54, p < .001; IT/support staff (N = 17), W = 129.5, SE = 18.36, z = 3.35, p < .001; and administrative staff (N = 18), W = 153.0, SE = 20.20, z = 3.79, p < .001. For students (N = 141), the observed median was equal to the hypothetical median of 3, yet the test still yielded a statistically significant result (W = 1,872, SE = 133.60, z = 6.70, p < .001), suggesting that the distribution of responses was skewed toward higher values despite the median remaining unchanged.

Figure 7 – Changes in the way your institution uses LLMs or GenAI tools for teaching, learning, or research

3.2.13. Changes in the way your institution uses LLMs or GenAI tools for teaching, learning, or research (open-ended answers)

The open-ended answers of the participants who said “Yes...” to the question “Compared to a year ago, have you noticed any changes in the way your institution uses LLMs or Generative AI tools for teaching, learning, or research?” indicated that it is evident that AI is increasingly being utilized and supported in teaching and learning. The usage of AI tools has expanded.

Philip (Teacher): In my experience, its use becomes more appropriate once the novelty and initial hype begin to subside. Certain practices, such as teaching, may begin to become established, and based on these, AI can be used more widely and appropriately than before.

Oscar (Administrator): We are seeking to build them into student support, engagement with academic content, and production of learning materials. Also to redesign teaching and assessment to enable students to make subject-appropriate use of them.

Angela (IT/Support): Students are encouraged and trained to use generative AI in the learning process. (Course Learning with AI designed for students of all faculties/degree programmes). AI is increasingly being used in administration.

Dan (IT/Support): Language models are now higher on the priority list for developing digital services.

3.2.14. Students were most unaware of nationwide practices in 2025

The Kruskal–Wallis test revealed a statistically significant difference between groups in their perceptions of nationwide practices related to the use of GenAI tools, $H(3) = 69.70$, $p < .001$. Post hoc pairwise comparisons showed that students consistently reported significantly lower awareness or perception of such practices compared to teachers ($p < .001$), IT/support staff ($p < .001$), and administrative staff ($p < .001$). Differences between teachers and IT/support staff ($p = .141$) and between teachers and administrative staff ($p = .070$) were not statistically significant after correction. No significant difference was found between IT/support and administrative staff ($p = 1.000$).

Figure 8 – Awareness of nationwide practices regarding AI tools in 2025

3.2.15. The overall perception of nationwide practices did not change from 2024 to 2025

A general linear model was conducted to examine the effects of group and year on perceptions of nationwide practices related to the use of GenAI tools. The model was statistically significant, $F(7, 1991) = 10.83, p < .001$, explaining 3.7% of the variance ($R^2 = .037$). The effect of group was significant, $F(3, 1991) = 16.95, p < .001$, indicating clear differences between respondent groups. In contrast, the effect of year was not significant, $F(1, 1991) = 0.26, p = .612$, and the interaction between year and group was also non-significant, $F(3, 1991) = 0.90, p = .441$.

Post hoc comparisons showed that students reported significantly lower awareness of nationwide practices than teachers (mean difference = $-0.34, p < .001$), IT/support staff ($-0.80, p < .001$), and administrative staff ($-0.83, p < .001$). Teachers also reported lower awareness than IT/support staff ($p = .031$), but the difference between teachers and administrative staff was marginal ($p = .054$). No significant difference was found between IT/support and administrative staff ($p = 1.000$).

Table 6- Perception of nationwide practices from 2024 to 2025

Group	2024 Mean	2024 SE	2025 Mean	2025 SE
Student	1.48	0.03	1.64	0.06
Teacher	1.86	0.08	1.87	0.11
IT/Support	2.43	0.28	2.22	0.28
Administration	2.15	0.39	2.46	0.26

3.2.16. Awareness of nationwide practices regarding AI tools in 2025 (open-ended answers)

The responses of those who answered "Yes, ..." to the question "Are there any nationwide practices regarding the use of LLMs or Generative AI tools in the country where your university is located?" were analysed. Some participants mentioned existing applications, assistants or service websites with chatbots. Some provided links for the practices.

Cassidy (Student): Foundations and various ministerially initiated projects in NRW, HRK also informs about them and initiates.

Zed (Administrator): Different implementations at the state level in North Rhine-Westphalia.

Seth (Administrator): Artificial intelligence in early childhood education and training – legislation and recommendations

It was observed that some participants provided national policies instead of practices. So, these answers are presented in the next question which is about national policies in order to offer a clear analysis.

3.2.17. Students reported lower awareness of national policies in 2025 and the overall perceived level of definition of policies was low

The Kruskal–Wallis test revealed a statistically significant difference between groups in their perceptions of national policies related to the use of GenAI tools in education, $H(3) = 38.35$, $p < .001$. Post hoc pairwise comparisons with Bonferroni correction showed that students reported significantly lower awareness of such policies compared to teachers ($p = .016$), IT/support staff ($p = .010$), and administrative staff ($p < .001$). Additionally, teachers reported significantly lower awareness than administrative staff ($p = .002$). No statistically significant differences were found between IT/support and administrative staff ($p = .673$), or between teachers and IT/support staff ($p = .441$) after correction.

Are there any national policies in your country related to the use of LLMs or Generative AI tools in education?

Figure 9 – Awareness of national policies regarding AI tools in 2025

3.2.18. The overall perception of nationwide policies didn't change from 2024 to 2025

A general linear model was conducted to examine the effects of group and year on perceptions of national policies related to the use of GenAI tools in education. The model was statistically significant, $F(7, 1992) = 5.91$, $p < .001$, explaining 2.0% of the variance ($R^2 = .020$). The effect of group was significant, $F(3, 1992) = 9.45$, $p < .001$, indicating clear differences between respondent groups. However, the effect of year was not statistically significant, $F(1, 1992) = 2.58$, $p = .108$, and the interaction between year and group was also non-significant, $F(3, 1992) = 0.46$, $p = .714$.

Post hoc comparisons showed that students reported significantly lower awareness of national policies than teachers (mean difference = -0.20 , $p = .011$), IT/support staff (-0.51 , $p = .007$), and administrative staff (-0.83 , $p < .001$). Teachers also reported significantly lower awareness than administrative staff (mean difference = -0.63 , $p = .005$), but not significantly different from IT/support staff ($p = .408$). No significant difference was found between IT/support and administrative staff ($p = 1.000$).

Table 7- Perception of nationwide policies from 2024 to 2025

Group	2024 Mean	2024 SE	2025 Mean	2025 SE
Student	1.56	0.03	1.63	0.06
Teacher	1.75	0.08	1.83	0.11
IT/Support	2.00	0.24	2.15	0.28
Administration	2.08	0.32	2.58	0.29

3.2.19. Awareness of nationwide policies regarding AI tools in 2025 (open-ended answers)

There was a low level of awareness among all participants regarding national policies in their country on the use of LLMs or GenAI tools in education. On the other hand, those who said “Yes,...” to this question referenced some national policies or European Union Regulation.

National-Level Ethical Guidelines and Strategic Plans: Some responses included national councils or ministries developing ethical use frameworks.

Marcia (Teacher): Spain has begun to implement national policies related to the use of Large Language Models (LLMs) and generative AI tools in education, primarily through its 2024 National Artificial Intelligence Strategy and also through the work of the Spanish Agency for the Supervision of Artificial Intelligence (AESIA).

John (IT/Support): In Turkey, while there is a National Artificial Intelligence Strategy (2021-2025) outlining broader goals, specific and comprehensive national standards or policies explicitly governing the use of Generative AI across all sectors are still largely under development. However, within the higher education sector, the Council of Higher Education (YÖK) has published ethical guidelines concerning the use of Generative AI. These guidelines offer direction primarily for universities and academic settings...

Ben (Student): The UK has clearly defined national policies for the use of Generative AI in education. The Department for Education provides official guidelines on ethical, safe, and effective AI use in schools and universities.

European Union Regulation: Some of the respondents mentioned EU-wide policies, including the AI Act and directives.

Thomas (Student): The European Union has done some regulations concerning the use of AI in Higher Education.

Charles (Student): ... Additionally, there are specific regulations such as: AI Act (EU): the European regulation on the use of artificial intelligence, with a risk-based classification and National guidelines...

Felicity (IT/Support): *In Spain, there are no single, mandated nationwide practices for Generative AI; instead, its use is shaped by a dual framework. The National AI Strategy (ENIA) actively promotes and funds AI research, talent, and infrastructure in higher education, encouraging institutions to innovate autonomously. Concurrently, all practices are governed by the EU AI Act, which sets regulatory boundaries focused on risk management and transparency.*

3.3. The results regarding the intended use of LLMs and GenAI tools

Research Question 2: For what specific educational purposes do the four groups of academic users currently use or plan to use LLMs and GenAI?

3.3.1. The use of artificial intelligence was similar across all groups in 2025

To investigate whether the use of LLMs and GenAI tools differed across participant groups in 2025, a Kruskal-Wallis test was conducted. The results indicated no statistically significant differences between groups ($H(3) = 6.394, p = .094$). Therefore, the null hypothesis was retained, suggesting that the distribution of responses regarding the use of these tools was similar across all groups.

Figure 10 - The use of LLMs and GenAI tools in 2025

3.3.2. The overall use of LLMs and GenAI tools increased from 2024 to 2025

A General Linear Model (GLM) was conducted to examine whether the use of LLMs and GenAI tools in study or research differed by year and participant groups. The analysis revealed statistically significant main effects for both group ($F(3, 1998) = 9.623, p < .001, \eta^2 = .014$) and year ($F(1, 1998) = 18.601, p < .001, \eta^2 = .009$), indicating that usage levels varied between groups and increased from 2024 ($M = 2.52$) to 2025 ($M = 3.06$). Additionally, a significant interaction effect was found between group and year ($F(3, 1998) = 3.025, p = .029, \eta^2 = .005$), suggesting that the increase in usage over time was not uniform across all groups.

Table 8- The overall use of LLMs and GenAI tools from 2024 to 2025

Group	2024 Mean	2024 SE	2025 Mean	2025 SE
Student	2.399	0.025	2.818	0.049
Teacher	2.855	0.060	3.190	0.080
IT/Support	3.261	0.188	3.407	0.174
Administration	2.846	0.250	3.250	0.184

3.3.2. The use of LLMs and GenAI tools in 2025 (open-ended answers)

The participants who answered “Yes” to the question “Do you use LLMs or Generative AI tools in teaching, learning, or research?” also described their practices in the next step. Based on the findings, students frequently use tools such as ChatGPT, Gemini, Poe, and DeepSeek while studying to do tasks such as translating articles, summarising long texts and comparing answers while studying. Teachers, on the other hand, use them to support the research process, produce academic content, and develop educational materials. IT/Support staff mentioned using GenAI tools in some cases to identify, analyse, integrate, and develop them. The last group of participants, the administrators, use AI tools to review their writing, prepare research reports, or create initial drafts of written documents. Examples are presented below.

Anna (Student): *I usually use it for information and suggestions for ideas in article and project writing processes. I will use it for video development and audio for the interactive learning material I will prepare within the scope of my training.*

Charlie (Teacher): *Primarily for the creation of topics/questions in Assignments and Final Exams.*

Roy (IT/Support): *I actively identify, and sometimes develop, the generative AI and language models that are most suitable for my learning, research, and professional work. My goal is to apply these tools to simplify real-world tasks and make various aspects of life and work easier.*

Frank (Administrator): *Proofreading, internet research, instructions for IT services, simple programming tasks.*

3.3.3. According to self-reports: the use of AI tools in higher education has increased at the national level over the past year according to those who have knowledge

A one-sample Wilcoxon signed-rank test was conducted to assess whether respondents perceived a change in how their country uses GenAI tools in higher education compared to a year ago. “I have no idea” was excluded from the Wilcoxon test. In all groups, the observed median was 4, and the results showed statistically significant differences from the hypothetical median of 3: students $W = 2,907$, $SE = 187.13$, $z = 7.72$, $p < .001$; teachers $W = 1,415.0$, $SE = 109.17$, $z = 6.41$, $p < .001$; IT/support $W = 66.0$, $SE = 10.94$, $z = 3.02$, $p = .003$; and administration $W = 120.0$, $SE = 17.05$, $z = 3.52$, $p < .001$. Note that over 60 % of Students have no idea if the situation has changed in their country over the year.

Compared to a year ago, have you noticed any changes in the way the country where your university is located uses LLMs or Generative AI tools for studying or research in the higher education sector?

Figure 11 – Change in the use of AI tools during last year in national level

3.3.4. Change in the use of AI tools during last year (open-ended answers)

Responses from the participants who said “Yes...” to the question “Compared to a year ago, have you noticed any changes in the way the country where your university is located uses LLMs or Generative AI tools for teaching, learning, or research in the higher education sector?” are grouped as follows.

Widespread Familiarity and Use: Various comments reflect that AI is more present in different areas. The use of AI tools and discussions about them have significantly increased.

Jessica (Student): Artificial intelligence has become increasingly visible and familiar, and people have begun to experiment with and practice using it.

Daisy (Student): Over the past year in Italy, the use of LLMs and Generative AI tools has significantly increased across education, business, and public services. Universities have begun integrating AI into teaching and research, while companies use it for customer service automation and content creation. The government has also initiated discussions on ethical AI use and digital innovation strategies.

Larry (IT/Support): Gradually, more users have become familiar with artificial intelligence (mainly LLM and generative AI and tools), its basics, and have even conducted some experiments of their own...

Edgar (Administrator): More people have become familiar with LLMs and are using it.

Integration of AI into Higher Education: According to respondents, AI-related topics, courses and programmes are becoming more widely included in their universities.

Tim (Student): All universities in Spain now offer courses related to AI.

Nick (Teacher): Artificial intelligence is applied as part of study modules, and study modules related to artificial intelligence are offered to teachers and students, often using artificial intelligence as a starting point. Through various training courses, staff learn more about the principles of artificial intelligence, which may encourage them to use it more.

Julia (IT/Support): Academically, certificate programs, associate degree and undergraduate programs are available at universities. Many scientific events are organized in a year.

Anna (IT/Support): It seems to be a shift in perception, with more educators now seeing GAI not just as a novel concept, but as a valuable tool for teaching and learning.

Strategic Plans or National Guidelines: Based on the responses provided by participants, some countries are currently developing or announcing frameworks, or guidelines for the use of AI in education. There are plans and efforts at the national level.

Stephen (Teacher): Compared to the previous year, there has been a notable increase in the awareness and utilization of generative AI tools within Spanish higher education institutions. This includes the development of institutional policies governing AI use, incorporation of AI-related content into curricula, and the establishment of dedicated AI research centers.

Leslie (IT/Support): Establishment of a cross-university AI infrastructure with commercial and open LLMs (KI.connect).

Marsha (Administrator): Government sponsored/run web sites for services to citizens now embed LLMs for facilitating Q&A with citizens. Professors and students seem to be using LLMs widely for research, as well as text polishing/generation.

3.4. The results regarding opportunities of LLMs and GenAI

Research Question 3: What opportunities do the four groups of academic users identify in relation to individual, institutional and national policies and practices concerning the use of GenAI in higher education?

The question “*What benefits/positive outcomes have you observed/ do you predict from using LLMs or Generative AI tools?*” is answered by all participants. Findings are summarized below.

Students

When asked about the benefits of AI, students overwhelmingly mentioned how GenAI tools help them work more efficiently. Utilizing AI tools is also timesaving. Therefore, *increased efficiency* and the *time-saving potential* are the most frequent benefits among students. *Academic help* is another significant benefit of AI in education. Those who mentioned the use of AI tools as beneficial in academic work specified that it supports the understanding of complex topics and the generation of ideas. They were also seen useful in brainstorming and simplifying research tasks. All these benefits make learning more personalized and thus accessible, by supporting learners with diverse needs. Some students also acknowledged that AI is really useful in enhancing writing skills. AI is seen as a learning partner among students, which can be understood clearly with the quotation below.

Charlotte (Student): *Significant time saving. In addition, “someone” to discuss with who is always interested when you have time.*

While acknowledging the value of accessing information easily, a few students mentioned their concern about the reliability of the answers provided by AI.

Teachers

Based on the responses, teachers agree that using AI offers various benefits. The most common benefit is *increased efficiency* and *saving time*. Utilizing AI tools helps reduce workload, speed up tasks, and boost efficiency and productivity by automating repetitive tasks. Teachers utilize AI for generating questions, creating summaries, preparing course materials, and translating foreign language texts to enhance their understanding. So, *support for academic tasks* is another benefit of using AI tools among teachers.

GenAI tools are also seen as valuable for tailoring education to individual needs. They offer *more personalized learning* by providing learning opportunities for students with different learning styles and giving tailored feedback. In light of the responses provided by teachers, integrating these tools into teaching is crucial for fostering critical thinking and digital literacy among students, preparing them for an AI-integrated future. The following response from a teacher summarized the mutual benefit of using AI in educational processes for both teachers and students:

Dean (Teacher): *Once you have learned how to use the tools yourself, you understand how they work better, which in turn supports your ability to discuss the topic with your students. This enables us to approach the use of artificial intelligence ethically and improve students' artificial intelligence text skills in their studies and future working life.*

IT/Support Staff and Administrators

Responses from IT Support and Administrative staff were analysed together due to their small number. Participants most commonly highlighted *efficiency in time and effort* as one of the main benefits of AI tools. Automating some repetitive, time-consuming academic and administrative tasks such as content creation, grading, and summarizing reports is highly beneficial for this group. There is faster and easier access to information, which leads to a reduction in workload. Efficiency gains allow institutions to devote more time to strategic initiatives rather than repetitive administrative tasks.

Misha (IT/Support): *In open and distance learning, LLMs and Generative AI tools offer the potential to create more personalized learning experiences tailored to individual student needs and pace. Additionally, they can significantly improve student support by providing instant feedback and round-the-clock assistance, enhancing accessibility for remote learners.*

This group also mentioned the potential of AI tools to offer learning support for students. The responses focus on AI's role in improving the learner experience by providing instant feedback and assistance, enhancing accessibility, and creating more engaging learning materials. Furthermore, increasing demand for AI enables students to enhance the quality of their contributions by learning about and practicing more with AI tools.

In conclusion, the use of LLMs and GenAI offers a wide range of benefits and positive outcomes for all stakeholder groups. Even if different groups had slightly different things to mention, they agreed on these benefits of using AI: *efficiency and productivity, time-saving potential, academic support, and more personalized and accessible learning.*

3.4. The results about challenges of LLMs and GenAI

Research Question 4: What challenges do the four groups of academic users describe concerning individual, institutional and national policies and practices governing the use of GenAI in higher education?

In response to the question “*What challenges (technical, ethical, pedagogical), if any, have you faced/do you oversee in using LLMs or Generative AI tools in education?*”, answers are summarized below.

Students

One of the featured themes among students regarding the challenges of using AI tools is *ethical concerns / responsible use*. Data privacy, plagiarism, biased outputs, or misuse of AI are among the most mentioned concerns of using AI.

There are also concerns about false or biased content, fact-checking, and trust in AI responses. Most students stated their skepticism about the reliability of AI-generated content. The constant need to check the accuracy of the information has resulted from this concern. Furthermore, there might be a possibility to learn incorrect information because of the unnoticed mistakes in AI-generated texts. Therefore, these challenges can be grouped as *information reliability and accuracy*.

Even if enhancement in critical thinking is a benefit mentioned by most of the participants in the previous question, relying too much on AI may lead to a decrease in critical thinking or creativity. Therefore, *over-reliance on AI* is another concern among students. Finding the balance is the thing that matters.

Katherine (Student): *A challenge may be finding a balance so that critical thinking and the acquisition of knowledge and skills do not weaken or disappear, given the ability to access a vast amount of information quickly and easily (sometimes inaccurate), which makes the above less necessary.*

The other theme regarding the challenges of using AI is *technical and accessibility challenges*. It seems that, without proper support, problems such as lack of digital skills or unfamiliarity with AI tools may create a barrier. Furthermore, not everyone or every institution has equal access. These aforementioned difficulties may prevent students from using, accessing, or understanding GenAI tools. Lastly, a few students explicitly stated that they haven’t faced problems using AI.

Teachers

Regarding the responses, *pedagogical concerns* are highlighted as a main challenge. Teachers are worried about how GenAI tools may affect the learning process, instructional quality and educational outcomes. Leaving these processes— adapting teaching methodologies, assessing student learning and providing feedback— to AI may create problems. Over-reliance by students is also another problem stated by teachers because it can undermine critical thinking. Students may become fully dependent on AI and stop thinking independently which leads to less engagement.

The responses from teachers also raise concerns about plagiarism, cheating, student honesty, therefore, misuse of AI tools. Avoiding critical thinking, creativity, or effort by overusing AI may jeopardize learning outcomes as stated by teachers. Therefore, *ethical concerns* are another challenge that teachers face.

Dwight (Teacher): *The biggest challenge in my work at the moment is that not all students are aware of the risks and ethical issues associated with artificial intelligence, and as a result, they resort to its fraudulent and unethical use...*

Several teachers also mentioned *technical concerns*. Infrastructure problems and integration with different platforms are among the problems stated by teachers. Although many teachers are willing to use AI, technical issues often stop it being adopted in a smooth and widespread way.

IT/Support Staff and Administrators

Responses from IT Support and Administrative staff were analysed together due to their small number. Privacy, security, fairness, and misuse of AI tools are among the concerns raised by this group. Some noted the difficulty in identifying AI-generated work which creates a blurry line between original work and AI. Therefore, *ethical and data protection concerns* are among the common themes.

Respondents also raised concerns about *information reliability and accuracy*. Among the concerns are the risk of hallucinations and the overall reliability of information generated by artificial intelligence systems. Following these challenges, a need for clear guidelines, institutional or national regulations regarding acceptable AI use is stated by the participants. The absence of structured policies may lead to ambiguity and ethical problems.

Natasha (IT/Support): *If the data generated through AI tools is used indiscriminately, and educators lack sufficient knowledge of the subject matter, there is a risk that unfiltered and potentially inaccurate information will be produced. This may lead to confusion among learners regarding the reliability and accuracy of the content. I believe that a general regulatory framework needs to be established in order to ensure the responsible use of AI in education. In other words, it is essential to define best practices as well as unacceptable uses.*

Moreover, *technical infrastructure and implementation* were raised as another common concern based on the responses. Some noted technical problems regarding integrating AI tools into existing systems. Some universities do not have sufficient technical expertise, leading to a decline in the efficiency of their departments. A few of the participants stated the need for additional training for both staff and students. A lack of AI literacy is seen as a barrier to AI adoption. Lastly, a few respondents mentioned lack of critical thinking resulting from over-reliance, the environmental impact and wide availability of paid AI tools.

In conclusion, all stakeholder groups composed of students, teachers, IT and administrators have agreed on some challenges regarding the use of GenAI tools. These can generally be described as *ethical concerns, information reliability and accuracy, and technical problems*.

3.6. Additional results regarding institutional and national policies and practices

Partners reported their university’s policies in last year's First Report (Koçdar et al., 2025). We asked partners to review their university’s policies in this document and answer the following item: “Compared to a year ago, have you noticed any changes in your university’s policies (rules, standards, recommendations, guidelines, regulations, etc.) related to the use of LLMs or Generative AI since October 2024?” The answers are presented in Table 9 (below).

Table 9- Institutional Policies in ADMIT Partner Universities

Institution	Change in policies	Additional Information
AU	No change	
FERNUNI	Yes, there are additional policies	The FernUniversität in Hagen (FeU) has updated the AI Guidelines 2.0 (April 2025) and Recommendations for Action 3.0 (July 2025). Both documents are advisory in character. Currently the FeU is developing an overarching AI strategy and planning guidelines for AI integration into exams. There is also a mandatory internal Regulation of Learning Analytics to ensure data privacy.
HOU	No change	
JYU	No change	
OUC	No change	
OOUKT	No change	
UNED	No change	
UNIDISTANCE	Yes, there are additional policies	A working group has been set up to develop an institution-wide AI policy and guidelines. They will be available in 2026.
UNINETUNO	No change	
UOC	Yes, there are additional policies	In 2025, UOC introduced SofIA, its internal advisory framework and guidelines for integrating AI across educational, administrative, and support services. SofIA aims to transform the university into an AI-enabled institution, enhancing teaching, learning, and operational processes. https://www.uoc.edu/en/news/2025/sofia-uoc-artificial-intelligence

Partners reported their university’s practices last year for the First Report (Koçdar et al., 2025). We asked partners to review their university’s practices and answer the following item: “Compared to a year ago, have you noticed any changes in your university’s practices (e.g. virtual assistant, automated grading, personalized learning, etc.) regarding the use of LLMs or Generative AI since October 2024?” The answers are presented in Table 10.

Table 10- Institutional Practices in ADMIT Partner Universities

Institution	Change in practices	Additional Information
AU	No change	
FERNUNI	Yes, there are additional practices	<p>A lot has changed since last year. In the meantime, KI:connect.nrw is used at the FernUniversität in Hagen. It offers a central portal for generative AI applications to all universities in North Rhine-Westphalia, accessible by both employees and students.</p> <p>Furthermore, the university provides and uses various AI tools across different areas of expertise and administration, including in-house developments and third-party solutions. For example, the COFFEE tool offers personalized AI-driven formative feedback for text assignments using course-specific evaluation criteria and context. Instructors can add contextual information (e.g., material excerpts) and establish custom criteria that set expectations for each task. These elements are sent to an AI model through quality-secured prompts, allowing students to receive immediate AI-generated feedback aligned with the defined criteria.</p> <p>To support educators and learners, the university has developed resources such as a Moodle (LMS) course titled “AI in teaching” aimed at teachers and tutors, an AI experimentation environment, and the AI-Campus Hub NRW. Teachers can integrate AI-Campus course materials into their own teaching.</p> <p>The university's website on "AI in Teaching" provides comprehensive information, including tool overviews and details for students, explaining generative AI concepts and its applications in learning—such as literature research, text revision, and translation. Additionally, it hosts workshops to help students leverage AI in their studies. Additionally, the website explores topics like copyright, exams, data protection, and accessibility.</p>
HOU	No change	
JYU	Yes, there are additional practices	<p>Communication and training on the use of AI tools has continued to increase. In 2025, a workspace entitled "Basics of artificial intelligence in university work – material for teachers, researchers, and support service staff" was published for university staff. The workspace is updated as new material is published.</p>
OUC	Yes, there are additional practices	<p>Establishment of AI committee, pilot tests of AI tools in learning design and IT support, seminars/workshops for staff, students and the general public on generative AI & LLMs</p>
OOUK	Yes, there are additional practices	<p>Over the past year, the university has consolidated a range of practices that embed the use of Generative AI across teaching, learning, assessment, and organisational processes. Work has centred on strengthening AI literacy for students and staff, supporting critical evaluation of AI outputs, and developing practical prompting skills for academic study. In assessment, new approaches ensure tasks are robust to the use of AI while maintaining academic integrity and providing differentiated support for diverse needs. Staff capacity has been enhanced through training and guidance on responsible AI use, ethics, and inclusivity, with particular emphasis on the EDIA lens and alignment with external frameworks such as the EU AI Act. Overall, practices have shifted from high-level guidance to concrete applications that drive innovation, inclusivity, and</p>

		consistency in educational provision.
UNED	Yes, there are additional practices	Several new guides focused on research tasks have been developed, in addition to those already available for teaching. All of these guides contain recommendations, except for the last one, which is mandatory. The guides are: 1) Guide to supporting research with AI. The UNED Library has published a guide that addresses the uses, limitations, and recommendations for AI tools in research (bibliographic searches, writing, text review). URL: https://investigauned.uned.es/nueva-guia-sobre-el-uso-de-herramientas-de-ia-para-el-apoyo-a-la-investigacion/ . Publication date: Nov 11, 2024; 2) Guide “How to declare the use of AI in academic work.” A section of Investiga UNED (Library) proposes structures to make the use of AI tools transparent: indicate which tools were used, for what purpose, to what extent, etc. URL: https://investigauned.uned.es/como-declarar-el-uso-de-ia-en-trabajos-academicos/ . Publication Date: May 14, 2025; 3) Guide “How to declare the use of AI in academic work.” Defines a policy for the use of AI in articles in a UNED journal. For the journal Estudios Institucionales (UNED), there is a specific policy: authors cannot attribute authorship to AI; AI (or assisted technologies) may only be used to improve language or readability; if used, it must be cited; authors are responsible for reviewing the validity of what the AI generates. URL: https://investigauned.uned.es/recomendaciones-eticas-para-la-investigacion-en-inteligencia-artificial/ . Publication date: May 13, 2024.
UNIDISTANCE	Yes, there are additional practices	A module on "Critical AI Literacy for Learning" will be offered to the students from autumn 2025.
UNINETTUNO	No change	
UOC	Yes, there are additional practices	Since October 2024, UOC has introduced and expanded operational practices through the LIS project. LIS uses LLMs and Generative AI for AI-based early-warning systems for students, AI-assisted feedback, empathic conversational agents, pilot projects for automated assessment, and personalized learning support tools https://blogs.uoc.edu/lis-project/about-lis/

Partners reported their country’s policies last year for the First Report (Koçdar et al., 2025). We asked partners to review their country’s policies and answer the following item: “Compared to a year ago, have you noticed any changes in your country’s policies related to the use of LLMs or Generative AI since October 2024?” The answers are presented in Table 11.

Table 11- Nationwide Policies in ADMIT Partner Universities

Institution	Change in policies	Additional Information
Türkiye	No change	
Germany	Yes, there are additional policies	In addition to the national and specific AI strategies for North Rhine-Westphalia, an AI strategy for the education sector is planned. Furthermore, the Federal Ministry of Research, Technology and Space has developed a High Tech Agenda. To implement the EU AI Regulation at both national and state levels, various activities are underway. For instance, in North Rhine-Westphalia, the KI:edu.nrw project has released a legal opinion on the significance of the European AI Regulation for universities. Additionally, the Legal Information Centre at FernUniversität in Hagen has developed guidelines for creating an AI policy within Open Resources Campus NRW, focusing on compliance issues.
Greece	No change	
Finland	Yes, there are additional policies	The Finnish National Agency for Education and the Ministry of Education and Culture have published (4/2025) the material "Artificial intelligence in education – legislation and recommendations in 2025". This material has been prepared in collaboration with individuals working in various positions in the education sector, researchers and experts from other stakeholders. Policies introduced in this material are merely advisory than binding. https://www.oph.fi/en/artificial-intelligence-education-legislation-and-recommendations
Cyprus	Yes, there are additional policies	Criminalization of the use of artificial intelligence in the production of child pornography - 10April 2025, https://cyprus-mail.com/2025/04/10/cyprus-criminalises-ai-generated-child-pornography
United Kingdom	No change	
Spain	Yes, there are additional policies	In March 2025, the Spanish government approved a draft law (Anteproyecto de Ley para el Buen Uso y la Gobernanza de la IA) that aligns with the EU AI Act. (https://avance.digital.gob.es/layouts/15/HttpHandlerParticipacionPublicaAnexos.ashx?k=19128)
Italy	Yes, there are additional policies	In any school, since fall 2015, it is completely forbidden to use any smartphone etc. It is not a direct change of the policy about AI but obviously this regulation will impact the use of AI tools during the hours on class room.
Switzerland	Yes, there are additional policies	There are Guidelines on Artificial Intelligence for the Confederation published July 1st, 2025. And a report on AI in Education by the SERI, July 2nd 2025.

Partners reported their country’s nationwide practices in our First Report (Koçdar et al., 2025) We asked partners to review their country’s nationwide practices and answer the following item: “Compared to a year ago, have you noticed any changes in your country’s nationwide practices regarding the use of LLMs or Generative AI since October 2024?” The answers are presented in Table

Table 12- Nationwide Practices in ADMIT Partner Universities

Country	Change in Practices	Additional Information
Türkiye	No change	
Germany	Yes, there are additional practices	<p>Germany’s Federal Ministry for Research, Technology and Space is advancing digitalization in higher education through four key initiatives. The German Forum for Higher Education in the Digital Age (HFD) (https://hochschulforumdigitalisierung.de/en/) acts as a nationwide think-&-do tank. HFD brings together a broad community around digitalization in teaching and learning, makes developments visible, and tests innovative approaches to solutions. Complementing this effort is the Federal-State Initiative on AI in Higher Education. The third pillar, AI Campus, (https://ki-campus.org/) democratizes access to AI education with its comprehensive online platform offering resources, interactive courses, and collaborative projects for educators and students. Lastly, the ministry has established research funding on digital higher education across four lines.</p> <p>Since 2025, Stifterverband e.V. (https://www.stifterverband.org/english) has formed four working groups as part of the Alliance for Future Skills. For example, the ‘AI in Higher Education’ task force holds a monthly AI strategy briefing for university management and is drafting a paper on the future of higher education.</p> <p>In North Rhine-Westphalia, the AI Campus Hub NRW (based on the federal initiative ‘AI Campus’) bundles transfer and networking activities at regional level. KI:edu.nrw (cooperation of Digitale Hochschule NRW), OpenSource-KI.nrw and KI:connect.nrw are three state-funded projects that jointly address the challenge of consolidating the similar needs and issues faced by many universities in the state with regard to the use of generative AI services and providing central points of contact.</p>
Greece	No change	
Finland	No change	
Cyprus	Yes, there are additional practices	Establishment of a National Specialized Committee (task force) on AI, seminars/workshops on generative AI & LLMs in education
Netherlands		
United Kingdom	Yes, there are additional practices	In January 2025 the government published the AI Opportunities Action Plan laying out a bold roadmap for maximising AI’s potential to drive growth and deliver real benefits to people across the UK. https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/ai-opportunities-action-plan/ai-opportunities-action-plan#lay-the-foundations
Spain	No change	In 2024, CRUE (Conference of Spanish Rectors) published a document with recommendations for generative AI in university teaching (opportunities, risks, ethics, evaluation). (It is not law, but it guides the university system). Certain recommendations were made, but the implementation of practices was delegated to the universities: a) Agreement between universities on a series of guiding principles on the use of GAI in higher education to ensure the ethical and

		<p>responsible use of AI so that both teachers and students can use AI safely and accessibly, preserving equity and respecting data privacy and possible issues of copyright, intellectual property rights, etc. It is also necessary to make recommendations to teachers on their role with regard to AI and the educational process, i.e., when the process can be supported by AI and when teachers are responsible for the educational process. b) Definition of competencies with regard to the use of AI for students and teachers (prompt engineering, AI-based assessment, tutoring, etc.) as well as training programs for the achievement of these competencies. From now on, this training should also be considered in teacher training programs, explaining the opportunities, risks, how to avoid them, and possible tools. Analyze whether the proposed competencies fit within the competency framework of DigCompEdu. If not, it would be necessary to analyze the proposal for an update. c) Each university should facilitate internal discussion processes between the different groups (faculty, students, administrative and service staff, and any other interested entities) on the impact of AI on educational processes and how to adopt this technology while maximizing benefits and minimizing risks. Forums for the exchange of these discussions between universities should also be created. d) Plan the incorporation of AI in the university, taking into account aspects such as student-oriented functionality that enables quality education, reduction of the administrative burden on teachers to allow them more time for teaching processes with and for students, how to provide them with better information about their students, alternatives for personalization and formative assessment, costs, security, privacy, transparency of the models used, reduction of bias, and preservation of equity. This planning also analyzes curricula to identify content, competencies, and learning outcomes, methodologies, training activities, and assessments that will be introduced, modified, or eliminated due to the incorporation of AI. Within this analysis, one of the key aspects will be to promote the ethical use of these tools by students and critical thinking. e) Promote the formation of teaching communities within each university for the exchange of good practices regarding the use of AI in teaching (methodologies, prompts, tools, etc.). In turn, it would be desirable to form these groups at the national level to allow for the exchange of ideas, taking into account the national educational context. f) Explain to students how their data (personal, academic, etc.) will be handled in the AI applications introduced for teaching use and define processes for any group to report security, privacy, and equity issues in the use of AI. Processes should also be defined to monitor the possible effects on the student learning process, as well as the benefits to the teacher. g) Recommend the existence of an equal opportunities program in access to AI, or, alternatively, an access subsidy program for disadvantaged groups. h) Assess the total ecological cost of operating the IAG systems to be used, including their carbon footprint and whether or not they come from renewable sources. If public tenders are held, this aspect should be considered in the contract specifications. i) This technology is currently a breakthrough that will mature over time, as teachers receive training and become aware of its possibilities and risks. It is therefore necessary to monitor the evolution of the technology and how it can contribute to improving teaching. At the same time, we will see that other aspects associated with technology, such as ethical, legal, and</p>
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		data protection issues, will continue to develop, and we will need to be vigilant in order to implement any necessary changes as soon as possible, given the importance of these issues for individuals and society as a whole.
Italy	Yes, there are additional practices	In any school, since fall 2015, it is completely forbidden to use any smartphone etc. It is not a direct change of the policy about AI but obviously this regulation will impact the use of AI tools during the hours on class room.
Switzerland	No change	Faculties are developing and implementing guidelines for the use of GenAI in written research papers for students.

4. Conclusions

This section presents the key findings, limitations, and recommendations related to the observed trends in policies and practices concerning the use of LLMs and GenAI within the ADMIT project partnership in 2025.

4.1. Main findings

This report gives an overview of the current situation regarding policies and practices related to LLMs and GenAI during the second year of the ADMIT partnership. The results show that interest in and use of these technologies is increasing. At the same time, there are clear differences in how well different groups understand and apply them.

The findings reveal notable differences in familiarity with LLMs and GenAI among stakeholder groups in higher education. Students consistently reported lower levels of awareness compared to teachers, IT/support staff, and administrators. Although familiarity increased across all groups from 2024 to 2025, the relative differences between groups remained stable. This suggests that while overall awareness is growing, students may not be receiving the same level of exposure or support as professional staff. Indeed, students reported less access to formal training opportunities in 2025, and the data showed no significant change over time in the availability of support across groups. The types of training and support also varied: students relied more heavily on informal learning methods such as peer collaboration and online resources, whereas staff groups had greater access to structured training through workshops, seminars, and institutional programs. These disparities lead to a need for more inclusive and targeted support strategies to ensure that all members of the academic community can engage meaningfully with AI technologies.

Across all groups, compliance with standards and ethical principles (such as avoiding plagiarism, citing AI use, and protecting personal data) was commonly reported and appeared to increase from 2024 to 2025. Participants also emphasized the importance of fact-checking AI-generated content and using it critically rather than copying outputs directly.

Despite these shared values, students consistently reported significantly lower awareness of institutional and national policies compared to teachers, IT/support staff, and administrators. In 2025, students were the least aware of both institutional practices and nationwide frameworks, comparisons confirming statistically significant differences between students and all other groups. Moreover, students perceived institutional policies as poorly defined and were largely unaware of formal practices at their universities and national policies.

While overall awareness of institutional engagement with GenAI tools increased slightly from 2024 to 2025, the gap between students and other groups remained. Teachers and IT/support staff showed moderate awareness, while administrators reported the highest familiarity with national-level policies and initiatives.

Participants across all groups noted that GenAI tools are increasingly integrated into everyday academic and administrative tasks. The frequency of use in teaching, learning, and research has grown, and attitudes toward AI have shifted positively. Respondents described more intensive use of AI for research, course material development, and exam preparation, indicating a broader institutional adoption of GenAI technologies.

In summary, while ethical and responsible use of GenAI is widely acknowledged, students lag behind, other groups in awareness of formal policies and practices, particularly at the institutional and national levels. This highlights a need for clearer communication and targeted support to ensure equitable understanding and engagement with GenAI across all academic roles.

There was a clear increase in the use of LLMs and GenAI across all academic user groups in 2025. Compared to 2024, the adoption of these technologies has expanded significantly, reflecting a growing integration of AI into teaching, learning, and research practices. Students reported using GenAI tools. Typical use cases include translating academic texts, summarizing lengthy materials, comparing answers, and generating ideas for writing assignments. Teachers employ AI tools to facilitate both instructional and research activities. IT and Support Staff described using AI tools in more technical and strategic ways. Administrators utilize AI tools for a range of practical tasks, including proofreading, drafting reports, conducting online research, and performing basic programming.

In addition to individual-level practices, participants noted a broader shift at the national level. Respondents from various countries observed increased awareness and usage of AI tools in higher education, alongside the development of institutional policies, AI-related curricula, and national strategies. This suggests a transition from informal experimentation to more structured and strategic implementation of AI technologies across the sector.

The analysis revealed perceived opportunities associated with the use of LLMs and GenAI across different academic user groups. While the specific benefits vary slightly between groups, several common themes emerged: most notably increased efficiency, time savings, academic support, and the potential for more personalized and accessible learning. Students appreciate AI's ability to simplify complex topics, assist with writing, and personalize learning, describing it as a helpful and always-available learning companion. Teachers highlight AI's role in reducing workload and enabling tailored instruction, while also fostering students' digital literacy and ethical understanding of AI. IT and Support Staff emphasize the potential of AI to automate routine tasks and improve student support, especially in remote learning environments. Administrators value AI for streamlining administrative processes and improving access to information, allowing more focus on strategic priorities.

Overall, the main challenges across all groups include ethical concerns, information reliability, and technical limitations, underscoring the need for clearer policies and better support for responsible AI integration in higher education. Students identified ethical concerns such as data privacy, plagiarism, and biased outputs as key challenges in using AI tools. They also questioned the reliability of AI-generated content and expressed worries about over-reliance on AI potentially weakening critical thinking and creativity. In addition, technical and accessibility issues, including unequal access and lack of digital skills, were noted as barriers to effective use. Teachers emphasized pedagogical challenges, particularly the impact of AI on learning quality and student engagement. They were concerned about students misusing AI, relying on it too heavily, and avoiding independent thinking. Ethical issues such as cheating and plagiarism were frequently mentioned, along with technical difficulties in integrating AI tools into existing educational systems. IT and administrative staff raised concerns about data protection, fairness, and the lack of clear institutional or national guidelines for responsible AI use. They also highlighted technical infrastructure limitations and the need for more training and AI literacy. Challenges related to information reliability, environmental impact, and the dominance of paid AI tools were also mentioned.

4.2. Limitations

It is important to note that the dataset includes only a small number of responses from a limited selection of universities within the ADMIT partnership. As such, the findings should not be interpreted as a comprehensive representation of the broader situation across European higher education institutions. Rather, they offer a partial view that highlights certain trends and perspectives, while leaving room for further investigation and broader data collection. The sample used in this study can be characterized as a convenience sample. These sources were chosen based on accessibility rather than through systematic sampling across stakeholder groups available. Future research could address this limitation by incorporating a more systematic sampling strategy.

In addition, one of the aims of this Second Report was to examine temporal changes in views and awareness of AI in higher education by comparing the data sets from our First Report (Koçdar et al., 2025), based on 2024 data, with the data collected in 2025. In the analysis, a General Linear Model (GLM) was applied, even though the dependent variables were measured on ordinal scales. Strictly speaking, GLM is not ideally suited for ordinal data. However, variables measured using Likert scales are commonly used as dependent variables in GLM analyses. This practice falls into a methodological “grey area”. It is not without controversy, but it is widely accepted and frequently applied in research. Some scholars even advocate for its use (see, for example, Norman, 2010).

4.3. Future Work

In our previous report (Koçdar et al., 2025), it was recommended that future data collection should concentrate on quantitative data by excluding individual interviews and expanding the questionnaires with additional items. Also, it was suggested that sample sizes across partner universities should be more homogenous. These goals have now been achieved, and the authors expect that the third and final report will follow a similar approach. However, the final report will place even greater emphasis on tracking and discussing temporal changes in awareness and use of AI in higher education across the partner institutions involved in the ADMIT project.

5. References

Kocdar, S., Uçar, H., AYDIN, C. H., Uotinen, V., Waselius, T., Michael, L., & Antonaci, A. (2024). Report on Trends in Policies and Practices on the Use of LLMs and Generative AI in the Partnership. First Report. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14501248>

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Appendix A.

Questionnaire for ADMINISTRATION/UNIVERSITY MANAGEMENT The Use of Large Language Models (LLMs) and Generative AI in Education

This questionnaire is prepared as a part of EU co-funded project, titled as “generative Ai and large language Models In higher educaTion”, shortly ADMIT (<https://admit.eadtu.eu/>). The questionnaire intends to collect data from different stakeholders (students, teachers, administrators, staff) of partner higher education institutions to understand the current landscape, challenges, and opportunities associated with the use of Large Language Models (LLMs) and Generative AI tools, such as ChatGPT. This is the second data collection round for a 3-year project. The information gathered from this questionnaire will contribute to a broader understanding of the practical applications, policy implications, and future directions of LLMs and Generative AI tools in higher education.

In this questionnaire, **policy** refers to a formalized set of principles, rules, or guidelines adopted by an organization, institution, or governing body to direct decision-making and actions in using LLMs or Generative AI. On the other hand, **practice** refers to the actual implementation or enactment of ideas, policies, or theories in real-world settings. It encompasses the behaviors, actions, and routines of individuals or groups within institutional or professional contexts. The concepts of Generative AI and LLMs are considered *artificial intelligence (AI) based content-creation technologies, such as ChatGPT, designed to understand, generate, and work with human language.*

The questionnaire will take approximately 10-15 minutes to complete. Please answer all questions as honestly and accurately as possible. There are no right or wrong answers; we are interested in your experiences and perspectives. Some questions are open-ended to allow you to provide more detailed responses.

Thank you once again for your valuable contribution to this research. Your input will play a crucial role in shaping the future of education in the context of emerging AI technologies.

ADMIT Project Team

**I hereby acknowledge my acceptance of the [Consent Form] and express my willingness to participate in the study.*

Yes

No

(The questionnaire will be displayed when the response is 'YES'.)

General Information

- Name of the institution:
- Your position:
- Academic Degree: (multiple choice)
 - ❖ Associate
 - ❖ Bachelor's
 - ❖ Master's
 - ❖ Doctorate/PhD

1. Are you familiar with LLMs and Generative AI?

- *Yes, very familiar*
- *Yes, somewhat familiar*
- *No, not very familiar*
- *No, not familiar at all*

(No follow up -open ended- needed)

2. Have you received any training (formal or informal course, etc.) or support (teacher/expert/peer guidance, learning resources, etc.) related to the use of LLMs or Generative AI tools?

- *Yes, extensive training/support*
- *Yes, some training/support*
- *No, but I would like to receive training/support*
- *No, and I don't think I need training/support*

(The following item will appear for the ones who answer "Yes")

Please specify details about the training or support you received (Open-ended)

Individual Level

3. Do you use LLMs or Generative AI tools in teaching, learning, or research?

- Yes, I frequently use*
- Yes, I occasionally use*
- No, but planning to use*
- No, I don't use*

(The following item will appear for the ones who answer "Yes")

Please specify details about these practices. (Open-ended)

4. Do you follow specific standards, rules, or policies while using LLMs or Generative AI tools in teaching, learning, or research?

- Yes, I strictly follow*
- Yes, I somewhat follow*
- I do not follow them strictly*
- No, I do not follow them*

(The following item will appear for the ones who answer "Yes")

Please specify details about these standards, rules, or policies. (Open-ended)

5. Compared to your situation a year ago, have you noticed any changes in the way **you** use LLMs or Generative AI tools for teaching, learning, or research?

- Yes, I use them significantly more than a year ago*
- Yes, I use them slightly more than a year ago*
- No, my use has remained the same*
- Yes, I use them slightly less than a year ago*
- Yes, I use them significantly less than a year ago*
- I do not use them at all*

Follow-up (for those who answered “Yes”):

Please describe how your use of LLMs or Generative AI tools has changed over the past year. You may also share relevant examples or experiences. (Open-ended)

Institutional Level (Your university)

6. Are there any **institutional practices** (e.g. virtual assistant, automated grading, personalized learning, etc.) regarding the use of LLMs or Generative AI tools in your institution?

- *Yes, there are quite a number of practices*
- *Yes, there are a few practices*
- *No, but plans and discussions regarding the practices are ongoing*
- *No, there are no plans or discussions regarding practices*
- *I have no idea*

(The following item will appear for the ones who answer “Yes”)

Please specify the details about institutional practices. (Open-ended)

7. Are there any **institutional policies** (rules, standards, recommendations, guidelines, regulations, etc.) in your institution related to the use of LLMs or Generative AI tools?

- *Yes, clearly defined policies*
- *Yes, vaguely defined policies*
- *No, but policies are still being considered*
- *No policies exist at the moment*
- *I have no idea*

(The following item will appear for the ones who answer “Yes”)

Please specify details about institutional policies. You are also welcome to add a link to relevant web pages if you know them. (Open-ended)

8. Compared to a year ago, have you noticed any changes in the way **your institution** uses LLMs or Generative AI tools for teaching, learning, or research?

- *Yes, significant increase*
- *Yes, slight increase*
- *No change*
- *Yes, slight decrease*
- *Yes, significant decrease*
- *I have no idea*

Follow-up (for those who answered “Yes”):

Please describe how your institution’s use of LLMs or Generative AI tools has changed over the past year. You may also share relevant examples or experiences. (Open-ended)

National Level

9. Are there any **nationwide practices** regarding the use of LLMs or Generative AI tools in your country?

- *Yes, there are quite a number of practices*
- *Yes, there are a few practices*
- *No, but plans and discussions regarding the practices are ongoing*
- *No, there are no plans or discussions regarding practices*
- *I have no idea*

(The following item will appear for the ones who answer “Yes”)

Please specify the details about national practices. (Open-ended)

10. Are there any **national policies** in your country related to the use of LLMs or Generative AI tools in education?

- *Yes, clearly defined policies*
- *Yes, vaguely defined policies*
- *No, but policies are being developed*
- *No policies exist at the moment*
- *I have no idea*

(The following item will appear for the ones who answer “Yes”

Please specify details about relevant national policies in your country. You are also welcome to add a link to relevant web pages if you know them. (Open-ended)

11. Compared to a year ago, have you noticed any changes in the way **the country where your university is located** uses LLMs or Generative AI tools for teaching, learning, or research in the higher education sector?

- *Yes, the use has significantly increased*
- *Yes, the use has slightly increased*
- *No, there has been no change*
- *Yes, the use has slightly decreased*
- *Yes, the use has significantly decreased*
- *I have no idea*

Follow-up (for those who answered “Yes”):

Please describe how the use of LLMs or Generative AI tools has changed over the past year in the country where your university is located. You may also share relevant examples or experiences. (Open-ended)

Opportunities, Challenges and Others

12. What benefits/positive outcomes have you observed/ do you predict from using LLMs or Generative AI tools? (Open-ended)

13. What challenges (*technical, ethical, pedagogical*) if any, have you faced/do you oversee in using LLMs or Generative AI tools in education? (Open-ended).

14. Additional comments or suggestions (open ended)

Appendix B.

Questionnaire for IT/TEACHING AND LEARNING SUPPORT SERVICES The Use of Large Language Models (LLMs) and Generative AI in Education

This questionnaire is prepared as a part of EU co-funded project, titled as “generative **Ai** and **D** large language **Models** In higher educa**Tion**”, shortly ADMIT (<https://admit.eadtu.eu/>). The questionnaire intends to collect data from different stakeholders (students, teachers, administrators, staff) of partner higher education institutions to understand the current landscape, challenges, and opportunities associated with the use of Large Language Models (LLMs) and Generative AI tools, such as ChatGPT. This is the second data collection round for a 3-year project. The information gathered from this questionnaire will contribute to a broader understanding of the practical applications, policy implications, and future directions of LLMs and Generative AI tools in higher education.

In this questionnaire, **policy** refers to a formalized set of principles, rules, or guidelines adopted by an organization, institution, or governing body to direct decision-making and actions in using LLMs or Generative AI. On the other hand, **practice** refers to the actual implementation or enactment of ideas, policies, or theories in real-world settings. It encompasses the behaviors, actions, and routines of individuals or groups within institutional or professional contexts. The concepts of Generative AI and LLMs are considered *artificial intelligence (AI) based content-creation technologies, such as ChatGPT, designed to understand, generate, and work with human language.*

The questionnaire will take approximately 10-15 minutes to complete. Please answer all questions as honestly and accurately as possible. There are no right or wrong answers; we are interested in your experiences and perspectives. Some questions are open-ended to allow you to provide more detailed responses.

Thank you once again for your valuable contribution to this research. Your input will play a crucial role in shaping the future of education in the context of emerging AI technologies.

ADMIT Project Team

**I hereby acknowledge my acceptance of the [Consent Form] and express my willingness to participate in the study.*

Yes

No

(The questionnaire will be displayed when the response is 'YES'.)

General Information

- € Name of the institution:
- € Name of the Department:
- € Your position:
- € Academic Degree: (multiple choice)
 - ❖ Associate
 - ❖ Bachelor's
 - ❖ Master's
 - ❖ Doctorate/PhD

1. Are you familiar with LLMs and Generative AI?

- *Yes, very familiar*
- *Yes, somewhat familiar*
- *No, not very familiar*
- *No, not familiar at all*

(No follow up -open ended- needed)

2. Have you received any training (formal or informal course, etc.) or support (teacher/expert/peer guidance, learning resources, etc.) related to the use of LLMs or Generative AI tools?

- *Yes, extensive training/support*
- *Yes, some training/support*
- *No, but I would like to receive training/support*
- *No, and I don't think I need training/support*

(The following item will appear for the ones who answer "Yes")

Please specify details about the training or support you received (Open-ended)

Individual Level

3. Do you use LLMs or Generative AI tools in teaching, learning, or research?

- *Yes, I frequently use*
- *Yes, I occasionally use*
- *No, but planning to use*
- *No, I don't use*

(The following item will appear for the ones who answer "Yes")

Please specify details about these practices. (Open-ended)

4. Do you follow specific standards, rules, or policies while using LLMs or Generative AI tools in teaching, learning, or research?

- *Yes, I strictly follow*
- *Yes, I somewhat follow*
- *I do not follow them strictly*
- *No, I do not follow them*

(The following item will appear for the ones who answer "Yes")

Please specify details about these standards, rules, or policies. (Open-ended)

5. Compared to your situation a year ago, have you noticed any changes in the way **you** use LLMs or Generative AI tools for teaching, learning, or research?

- *Yes, I use them significantly more than a year ago*
- *Yes, I use them slightly more than a year ago*
- *No, my use has remained the same*
- *Yes, I use them slightly less than a year ago*
- *Yes, I use them significantly less than a year ago*
- *I do not use them at all*

Follow-up (for those who answered "Yes"):

Please describe how your use of LLMs or Generative AI tools has changed over the past year. You may also share relevant examples or experiences. (Open-ended)

Institutional Level (Your university)

6. Are there any **institutional practices** (e.g. virtual assistant, automated grading, personalized learning, etc.) regarding the use of LLMs or Generative AI tools in your institution?
- *Yes, there are quite a number of practices.*
 - *Yes, there are a few practices.*
 - *No, but plans and discussions regarding the practices are ongoing.*
 - *No, there are no plans or discussions regarding practices.*
 - *I have no idea.*

(The following item will appear for the ones who answer “Yes”)

Please specify the details about institutional practices. (Open-ended)

7. Are there any **institutional policies** (rules, standards, recommendations, guidelines, regulations, etc.) in your institution related to the use of LLMs or Generative AI tools?
- *Yes, clearly defined policies*
 - *Yes, vaguely defined policies*
 - *No, but policies are still being considered*
 - *No policies exist at the moment*
 - *I have no idea*

(The following item will appear for the ones who answer “Yes”)

Please specify details about institutional policies. You are also welcome to add a link to relevant web pages if you know them. (Open-ended)

8. Compared to a year ago, have you noticed any changes in the way **your institution** uses LLMs or Generative AI tools for teaching, learning, or research?

- *Yes, significant increase*
- *Yes, slight increase*
- *No change*
- *Yes, slight decrease*
- *Yes, significant decrease*
- *I have no idea*

Follow-up (for those who answered “Yes”):

Please describe how your institution’s use of LLMs or Generative AI tools has changed over the past year. You may also share relevant examples or experiences. (Open-ended)

National Level

9. Are there any **nationwide practices** regarding the use of LLMs or Generative AI tools in your country?

- *Yes, there are quite a number of practices*
- *Yes, there are a few practices*
- *No, but plans and discussions regarding the practices are ongoing*
- *No, there are no plans or discussions regarding practices*
- *I have no idea*

(The following item will appear for the ones who answer “Yes”)

Please specify the details about national practices. (Open-ended)

10. Are there any **national policies** in your country related to the use of LLMs or Generative AI tools in education?

- *Yes, clearly defined policies*
- *Yes, vaguely defined policies*
- *No, but policies are being developed*
- *No policies exist at the moment*
- *I have no idea*

(The following item will appear for the ones who answer “Yes”

Please specify details about relevant national policies in your country. You are also welcome to add a link to relevant web pages if you know them. (Open-ended)

11. Compared to a year ago, have you noticed any changes in the way **the country where your university is located** uses LLMs or Generative AI tools for teaching, learning, or research in the higher education sector?

- *Yes, the use has significantly increased*
- *Yes, the use has slightly increased*
- *No, there has been no change*
- *Yes, the use has slightly decreased*
- *Yes, the use has significantly decreased*
- *I have no idea*

Follow-up (for those who answered “Yes”):

Please describe how the use of LLMs or Generative AI tools has changed over the past year in the country where your university is located. You may also share relevant examples or experiences. (Open-ended)

Opportunities, Challenges and Others

12. What benefits/positive outcomes have you observed/ do you predict from using LLMs or Generative AI tools? (Open-ended)

13. What challenges (*technical, ethical, pedagogical*) if any, have you faced/do you oversee in using LLMs or Generative AI tools in education? (Open-ended).

14. Additional comments or suggestions (open ended) (Optional)

Appendix C.

Questionnaire for TEACHERS

Use of Large Language Models (LLMs) and Generative AI in Education

This questionnaire is prepared as a part of EU co-funded project, titled as “generative **AI** and **LLMs** in higher education”, shortly ADMIT (<https://admit.eadtu.eu/>). The questionnaire intends to collect data from different stakeholders (students, teachers, administrators, staff) of partner higher education institutions to understand the current landscape, challenges, and opportunities associated with the use of Large Language Models (LLMs) and Generative AI tools, such as ChatGPT. This is the second data collection round for a 3-year project. The information gathered from this questionnaire will contribute to a broader understanding of the practical applications, policy implications, and future directions of LLMs and Generative AI tools in higher education.

In this questionnaire, **policy** refers to a formalized set of principles, rules, or guidelines adopted by an organization, institution, or governing body to direct decision-making and actions in using LLMs or Generative AI. On the other hand, **practice** refers to the actual implementation or enactment of ideas, policies, or theories in real-world settings. It encompasses the behaviors, actions, and routines of individuals or groups within institutional or professional contexts. The concepts of Generative AI and LLMs are considered artificial intelligence (AI) based content-creation technologies, such as ChatGPT, designed to understand, generate, and work with human language.

The questionnaire will take approximately 10-15 minutes to complete. Please answer all questions as honestly and accurately as possible. There are no right or wrong answers; we are interested in your experiences and perspectives. Some questions are open-ended to allow you to provide more detailed responses.

Thank you once again for your valuable contribution to this research. Your input will play a crucial role in shaping the future of education in the context of emerging AI technologies.

ADMIT Project Team

**I hereby acknowledge my acceptance of the [Consent Form] and express my willingness to participate in the study.*

- Yes
- No

(The questionnaire will be displayed when the response is 'YES'.)

General Information

- Name of the Institution:
- Department or field of study:
- Number of years in teaching:
- Academic Title: (multiple choice)
 - ☒ Lecturer/University teacher
 - ☒ Assistant Professor
 - ☒ Associate Professor
 - ☒ Full Professor
 - ☒ Other

1. Are you familiar with LLMs and Generative AI?

- *Yes, very familiar*
- *Yes, somewhat familiar*
- *No, not very familiar*
- *No, not familiar at all*

(No follow up -open ended- needed)

2. Have you received any training (formal or informal course, etc.) or support (teacher/expert/peer guidance, learning resources, etc.) related to the use of LLMs or Generative AI tools?

- *Yes, extensive training/support*
- *Yes, some training/support*
- *No, but I would like to receive training/support*
- *No, and I don't think I need training/support*

(The following item will appear for the ones who answer "Yes")

Please specify details about the training or support you received (Open-ended)

Individual Level

3. Do you use LLMs or Generative AI tools in teaching, learning, or research?

- *Yes, I frequently use*
- *Yes, I occasionally use*
- *No, but planning to use*
- *No, I don't use*

(The following item will appear for the ones who answer "Yes")

Please specify details about these practices. (Open-ended)

4. Do you follow specific standards, rules, or policies while using LLMs or Generative AI tools in teaching, learning, or research?
- *Yes, I strictly follow*
 - *Yes, I somewhat follow*
 - *I do not follow them strictly*
 - *No, I do not follow them*

(The following item will appear for the ones who answer "Yes")

Please specify details about these standards, rules, or policies. (Open-ended)

5. Compared to your situation a year ago, have you noticed any changes in the way **you** use LLMs or Generative AI tools for teaching, learning, or research?
- *Yes, I use them significantly more than a year ago*
 - *Yes, I use them slightly more than a year ago*
 - *No, my use has remained the same*
 - *Yes, I use them slightly less than a year ago*
 - *Yes, I use them significantly less than a year ago*
 - *I do not use them at all*

Follow-up (for those who answered "Yes"):

Please describe how your use of LLMs or Generative AI tools has changed over the past year. You may also share relevant examples or experiences. (Open-ended)

Institutional Level (Your university)

6. Are there any **institutional practices** (e.g. virtual assistant, automated grading, personalized learning, etc.) regarding the use of LLMs or Generative AI tools in your institution?
- *Yes, there are quite a number of practices*
 - *Yes, there are a few practices*
 - *No, but plans and discussions regarding the practices are ongoing*
 - *No, there are no plans or discussions regarding practices*
 - *I have no idea*

(The following item will appear for the ones who answer “Yes”)

Please specify the details about institutional practices. (Open-ended)

7. Are there any **institutional policies** (rules, standards, recommendations, guidelines, regulations, etc.) in your institution related to the use of LLMs or Generative AI tools?
- *Yes, clearly defined policies*
 - *Yes, vaguely defined policies*
 - *No, but policies are being considered*
 - *No policies exist at the moment*
 - *I do not know / I cannot say*

(The following item will appear for the ones who answer “Yes”)

Please specify details about institutional policies. You are also welcome to add a link to relevant web pages if you know them. (Open-ended)

8. Compared to a year ago, have you noticed any changes in the way **your institution** uses LLMs or Generative AI tools for teaching, learning, or research?
- *Yes, significant increase*
 - *Yes, slight increase*
 - *No change*
 - *Yes, slight decrease*
 - *Yes, significant decrease*

- *I have no idea*

Follow-up (for those who answered “Yes”):

Please describe how your institution’s use of LLMs or Generative AI tools has changed over the past year. You may also share relevant examples or experiences. (Open-ended)

National Level

9. Are there any **nationwide practices** regarding the use of LLMs or Generative AI tools in your country?
- *Yes, there are quite a number of practices*
 - *Yes, there are a few practices*
 - *No, but plans and discussions regarding the practices are ongoing*
 - *No, there are no plans or discussions regarding practices*
 - *I have no idea*

(The following item will appear for the ones who answer “Yes”)

Please specify the details about national practices. (Open-ended)

10. Are there any **national policies** in your country related to the use of LLMs or Generative AI tools in education?
- *Yes, clearly defined policies*
 - *Yes, vaguely defined policies*
 - *No, but policies are being developed*
 - *No policies exist at the moment*
 - *I do not know / I cannot say*

(The following item will appear for the ones who answer “Yes”)

Please specify details about relevant national policies in your country. You are also welcome to add a link to relevant web pages if you know them. (Open-ended)

11. Compared to a year ago, have you noticed any changes in the way **the country where your university is located** uses LLMs or Generative AI tools for teaching, learning, or research in the higher education sector?

- *Yes, the use has significantly increased*
- *Yes, the use has slightly increased*
- *No, there has been no change*
- *Yes, the use has slightly decreased*
- *Yes, the use has significantly decreased*
- *I have no idea*

Follow-up (for those who answered “Yes”):

Please describe how the use of LLMs or Generative AI tools has changed over the past year in the country where your university is located. You may also share relevant examples or experiences. (Open-ended)

Opportunities, Challenges, and Others

12. What benefits/positive outcomes have you observed/ do you predict from using LLMs or Generative AI tools? (Open-ended)

13. What challenges (*technical, ethical, pedagogical*) if any, have you faced/do you oversee in using LLMs or Generative AI tools in education? (Open-ended).

14. Additional comments or suggestions (open-ended) (Optional)

Appendix D.

Questionnaire for STUDENTS Use of Large Language Models (LLMs) and Generative AI in Education

This questionnaire is prepared as a part of EU co-funded project, titled as “generative Ai and Large language Models In higher education”, shortly ADMIT (<https://admit.eadtu.eu/>). The questionnaire intends to collect data from different stakeholders (students, teachers, administrators, staff) of partner higher education institutions to understand the current landscape, challenges, and opportunities associated with the use of Large Language Models (LLMs) and Generative AI tools, such as ChatGPT. This is the second data collection round for a 3-year project. The information gathered from this questionnaire will contribute to a broader understanding of the practical applications, policy implications, and future directions of LLMs and Generative AI tools in higher education.

In this questionnaire, **policy** refers to a formalized set of principles, rules, or guidelines adopted by an organization, institution, or governing body to direct decision-making and actions in using LLMs or Generative AI. On the other hand, **practice** refers to the actual implementation or enactment of ideas, policies, or theories in real-world settings. It encompasses the behaviors, actions, and routines of individuals or groups within institutional or professional contexts. The concepts of Generative AI and LLMs are considered artificial intelligence (AI) based content-creation technologies, such as ChatGPT, designed to understand, generate, and work with human language.

The questionnaire will take approximately 10-15 minutes to complete. Please answer all questions as honestly and accurately as possible. There are no right or wrong answers; we are interested in your experiences and perspectives. Some questions are open-ended to allow you to provide more detailed responses.

Thank you once again for your valuable contribution to this research. Your input will play a crucial role in shaping the future of education in the context of emerging AI technologies.

ADMIT Project Team

**I hereby acknowledge my acceptance of the [Consent Form] and express my willingness to participate in the study.*

- Yes
- No

(The questionnaire will be displayed when the response is 'YES'.)

General Information

- Name of the Institution
- Department or field of study:
- Ongoing Academic Degree: (multiple choice)
 - ❖ Associate
 - ❖ Bachelor's
 - ❖ Master's
 - ❖ Doctorate/PhD

1. Are you familiar with LLMs and Generative AI?

- *Yes, very familiar*
- *Yes, somewhat familiar*
- *No, not very familiar*
- *No, not familiar at all*

(No follow up -open ended- needed)

2. Have you received any training (formal or informal course, etc.) or support (teacher/expert/peer guidance, learning resources, etc.) related to the use of LLMs or Generative AI tools?

- *Yes, extensive training/support*
- *Yes, some training/support*
- *No, but I would like to receive training/support*
- *No, and I don't think I need training/support*

(The following item will appear for the ones who answer "Yes")

Please specify details about the training or support you received (Open-ended)

Individual

Level

3. Do you use LLMs or Generative AI tools in studying or research?

- *Yes, I frequently use*

- *Yes, I occasionally use*
- *No, but planning to use*
- *No, I don't use*

(The following item will appear for the ones who answer "Yes")

Please specify details about how you use these tools. (Open-ended)

4. Do you follow specific standards, rules, or policies while using LLMs or Generative AI tools in studying or research?

- *Yes, I strictly adhere to available standards, rules or policies.*
- *Yes, I adhere to them to some extent.*
- *No, I do not strictly adhere to them.*
- *No, I do not adhere to them at all.*

(The following item will appear for the ones who answer "Yes")

Please specify details about these standards, rules, or policies. (Open-ended)

5. Compared to your situation a year ago, have you noticed any changes in the way **you** use LLMs or Generative AI tools for studying or research?

- *Yes, I use them significantly more than a year ago*
- *Yes, I use them slightly more than a year ago*
- *No, my use has remained the same*
- *Yes, I use them slightly less than a year ago*
- *Yes, I use them significantly less than a year ago*
- *I do not use them at all*

Follow-up (for those who answered "Yes"):

Please describe how your use of LLMs or Generative AI tools has changed over the past year. You may also share relevant examples or experiences. (Open-ended)

Institutional Level (Your university)

6. Are there any **institutional practices** (e.g. virtual assistant, automated grading, personalized learning, etc.) regarding the use of LLMs or Generative AI tools in your institution?

- *Yes, there are quite a number of practices*
- *Yes, there are a few practices*
- *No, but plans and discussions regarding the practices are ongoing*
- *No, there are no plans or discussions regarding practices*
- *I have no idea*

(The following item will appear for the ones who answer “Yes”)

Please specify the details about institutional practices. (Open-ended)

7. In your knowledge, are there any **institutional policies** (rules, standards, recommendations, guidelines, regulations, etc.) in your institution related to the use of LLMs or Generative AI tools?

- *Yes, clearly defined policies*
- *Yes, vaguely defined policies*
- *No, but policies are still being considered*
- *No policies exist at the moment*
- *I have no idea*

(The following item will appear for the ones who answer “Yes”)

Please specify details about institutional policies. You are also welcome to add a link to relevant web pages if you know them. (Open-ended)

8. Compared to a year ago, have you noticed any changes in the way **your institution** uses LLMs or Generative AI tools for studying or research?

- *Yes, significant increase*
- *Yes, slight increase*
- *No change*
- *Yes, slight decrease*
- *Yes, significant decrease*
- *I have no idea*

Follow-up (for those who answered “Yes”):

Please describe how your institution's use of LLMs or Generative AI tools has changed over the past year. You may also share relevant examples or experiences. (Open-ended)

National Level

9. Are there any **nationwide practices** regarding the use of LLMs or Generative AI tools in the country where your university is located?

- *Yes, there are quite a number of practices*
- *Yes, there are a few practices*
- *No, but plans and discussions regarding the practices are ongoing*
- *No, there are no plans or discussions regarding practices*
- *I have no idea*

(The following item will appear for the ones who answer "Yes")

Please specify the details about national practices. (Open-ended)

10. Are there any **national policies** related to the use of LLMs or Generative AI tools in education in the country where your university is located?

- *Yes, clearly defined policies*
- *Yes, vaguely defined policies*
- *No, but policies are being developed*
- *No policies exist at the moment*
- *I have no idea*

(The following item will appear for the ones who answer "Yes")

Please specify details about relevant national policies in your country. You are also welcome to add a link to relevant web pages if you know them. (Open-ended)

11. Compared to a year ago, have you noticed any changes in the way **the country where your university is located** uses LLMs or Generative AI tools for studying or research in the higher education sector?

- *Yes, the use has significantly increased*
- *Yes, the use has slightly increased*
- *No, there has been no change*
- *Yes, the use has slightly decreased*
- *Yes, the use has significantly decreased*

- *I have no idea*

Follow-up (for those who answered “Yes”):

Please describe how the use of LLMs or Generative AI tools has changed over the past year in the country where your university is located. You may also share relevant examples or experiences. (Open-ended)

Opportunities, Challenges, and Others

12. What benefits/positive outcomes have you observed/ do you predict from using LLMs or Generative AI tools? (Open-ended)

13. What challenges (*technical, ethical, pedagogical*) if any, have you faced/do you oversee in using LLMs or Generative AI tools in education? (Open-ended).

14. Additional comments or suggestions (Open-ended) (Optional)

Appendix E.

Consent Form for Questionnaires

This questionnaire aims to understand the current landscape, challenges, and opportunities associated with the use of Large Language Models (LLMs) and Generative AI such as ChatGPT, within your institution. The study is part of the EU funded project titled as *ADMIT: generative Ai and large language Models In higher educaTion*, and its results will shed light on a broader understanding of the practical applications, policy implications, and future directions of LLM and Generative AI technologies in education. To accomplish this, we will inquire about your individual experiences with LLMs and Generative AI technologies, as well as the policies and practices related to these technologies at both your institution and within your country. This is the second data collection round for a 3-year project.

Your participation in this study is entirely voluntary, and you may withdraw at any time without penalty. In alignment with the study's objectives, data will be collected through an online questionnaire. The questionnaire will take approximately 10-15 minutes to complete. Please rest assured that all responses will be treated with the highest confidentiality. You are not required to provide any information that could reveal your identity. To ensure the utmost security and confidentiality, the data will be stored in a secure Google Cloud repository, protected by robust encryption methods both during transmission and at rest. Access to this data will be strictly controlled, limited to authorized project partners only, and managed through secure access controls and authentication mechanisms. The data will be retained for the duration of the project, after which it will be securely discarded. At no point will the data be shared with third parties, upholding our commitment to participant privacy and data security. You have the right to review the data collected from you if desired.

No part of the data collection process will involve questions or requests that may cause discomfort. However, if you feel uncomfortable at any point during your participation, you have the option to withdraw from the study by sending an email to the contact address provided below. Should you choose to leave, any data collected from you will be promptly removed and discarded.

Thank you for taking the time to read and consider this voluntary participation form. Should you have any questions about the study, please direct them to [**Contact Name and email**] from the [**Department Name**] at [**University Name**].

Appendix F.

ADMIT-WP3-Policies and Practices-Additional Information for the Second Report

Dear Partners,

The aim of this short questionnaire is to gather additional information on current policies and practices regarding the use of LLMs or Generative AI tools in your institution and country for D3.2. This will complement and confirm the responses collected earlier from students, teachers, administrators, and support staff.

We kindly request that each partner conduct a brief review of their country and institution to ensure the most accurate and up-to-date reflection of current policies and practices. Please have one of the ADMIT Project team members at your institution complete the following short questionnaire by 15 September 2025.

Thank you,
WP3 Team

- Institution Name:

1. You reported **your university’s policies** last year for the *Report on Trends in Policies and Practices on the Use of LLMs and Generative AI in the Partnership – First Report*, available at: <https://zenodo.org/records/14501248>. Please review your university’s policies listed in Table 9, in the “**Policies**” column under the heading 3.6. *Additional results regarding institutional and national policies and practices* on page 31.

Compared to a year ago, have you noticed any changes in your university’s policies (rules, standards, recommendations, guidelines, regulations, etc.) related to the use of LLMs or Generative AI since October 2024?

- Yes, there are additional policies
- No change
- I don’t know

(The following item will appear if the answer is “Yes”)

Please provide details about the additional institutional policies and indicate whether these policies are **mandatory** (binding) or **advisory**. Include links to relevant web pages, if available. If applicable, also provide the publication date of these policies or recommendations.

If available, please upload any documents related to your institution’s policies (Word or PDF format).

2. You reported **your university's practices** last year for the *Report on Trends in Policies and Practices on the Use of LLMs and Generative AI in the Partnership – First Report*, available at: <https://zenodo.org/records/14501248>. Please review your university's practices listed in Table 9, in the “**Practices**” column on page 31.

Compared to a year ago, have you noticed any changes in your university's practices (e.g. virtual assistant, automated grading, personalized learning, etc.) regarding the use of LLMs or Generative AI since October 2024?

- Yes, there are additional practices
- No change
- I don't know

(The following item will appear if the answer is “Yes”)

Please specify the details about additional institutional practices.

3. You reported **your country's policies** last year for the *Report on Trends in Policies and Practices on the Use of LLMs and Generative AI in the Partnership – First Report*, available at: <https://zenodo.org/records/14501248>. Please review your country's policies listed in Table 10, in the “**Policies**” column on page 34.

Compared to a year ago, have you noticed any changes in your country's policies related to the use of LLMs or Generative AI since October 2024?

- Yes, there are additional policies
- No change
- I don't know

(The following item will appear if the answer is “Yes”)

Please provide details about the additional national policies and indicate whether these policies are **mandatory** (binding) or **advisory**. Include links to relevant web pages, if available. If applicable, also provide the publication date of these policies or recommendations.

If available, please upload any documents related to your country's additional policies (Word or PDF format).

4. You reported **your country's nationwide practices** last year for the *Report on Trends in Policies and Practices on the Use of LLMs and Generative AI in the Partnership – First Report*, available at: <https://zenodo.org/records/14501248>. Please review your country's nationwide practices listed in Table 10, in the “**Practices**” column on page 34.

Compared to a year ago, have you noticed any changes in your country's nationwide practices regarding the use of LLMs or Generative AI since October 2024?

Yes, there are additional practices

No change

I don't know

(The following item will appear if the answer is "Yes")

Please specify the details about your country's nationwide practices.

5.Additional Comments (if any)

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